

Modelling radial transport in the magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn and its coupling to planetary rotation

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1 Introduction

1.1 From astrophysical tori to giant planet systems

The physical processes involved in the equilibrium and dynamics of self-gravitating and/or magnetised neutral gas, plasma and dust tori have a wide range of applications for the understanding of astrophysical systems across a broad variety of scales, from the formation of gas giant planets in proto-planetary disks and of stars in interstellar clouds to the understanding of accretion disks around black holes and active galactic nuclei. . . Modelling the interaction of a disk with a central object is key to peering into the formation and evolution processes of planets, stars and galaxies. During planetary formation, it is very likely that disks form at both circumstellar and circumplanetary scales, leading to a complex interplay between disks, planets and stars.

In our Solar System, all planets except Venus and Mars display strong magnetic fields which form around each planet a magnetic cavity - the magnetosphere - which partly isolates their space environments from the surrounding interplanetary medium and solar wind. Among them, giant planets stand out by their strong magnetic fields and fast rotation rates, ranging from about 10 hours for Jupiter and Saturn to about 16 hours for Uranus and Neptune. Their magnetospheres are so extended that they encompass the orbits of all their regular moons, resulting in a variety of moon-magnetosphere interactions. The importance of the interactions between each planet, its moons and its magnetosphere dates back to the time of their formation, during which the combined effect of their gravitational and magnetic fields led to the formation of self-gravitating sub-systems of rings, disks and moons within the Solar System. The largest and most massive among them, the Jovian system has multiple analogues in stellar systems. The Jupiter-Io and Jupiter-Ganymede sub-systems are strong radio emitters which could be representative of the interaction between a close planet and its magnetised host star (Zarka et al. 2018), and the Laplace mean-motion resonance between the three Galilean moons Io, Europa and Ganymede was shown to have an analogue in the TRAPPIST-I system (Luger et al. 2017). Additionally, Batygin and Morbidelli 2020 develop an alternative scenario of the formation of Jovian-like systems and associated satellites based on a circumplanetary *decretion disk*, in which matter injected at high latitudes from the circumstellar flows through the disk outwards, and which is reminiscent of the radial outflow of matter presently observed in the disks around Jupiter and Saturn (Bagenal and Delamere 2011). The Jovian and Kronian sub-systems thus provide a unique opportunity to study the general properties of magnetised disks, their behaviour under the magnetic and gravitational field of the rotating central body and their interactions with surrounding companions, as well as the surrounding (interplanetary) medium. In addition, these "miniature planetary systems" have been studied in situ by several space probes, leading to a deeper understanding of the physical processes at play.

The Pioneer 10 and 11 flybys of Jupiter provided the first evidence of a strong radial bent of the Jovian magnetic field, associated to the presence of an equatorial current sheet (e.g. Goertz 1979), and the Jovian magnetic field has later been modelled by Connerney et al. 1981 based on Voyager I and II measurements in 1979. The study of Galileo data allowed one to derive the plasma properties through the disk (e.g. Bagenal, Wilson, et al. 2016), and since 2016, the on-going Juno mission has been providing crucial insight on the interaction between Galilean moons, the magnetosphere and the planet (e.g. Mura et al. 2017, Allegrini et al. 2020). At Saturn, Pioneer and Voyager measurements led, among other findings, to the identification and characterization of multiple plasma sources in the system (e.g. Richardson and Eviatar 1987). Later, the Cassini mission provided rich insight into the spatial and temporal variability of its magnetosphere and plasma populations and their interactions with moons and rings (e.g. Sergis et al. 2017, Staniland et al. 2020). Our general knowledge of the magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn is reviewed in the following section.

Figure 1: Io (left) and Enceladus (right), two volcanic moons in the magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn respectively. The plumes produced at the surface of the moon (left) feed tori which extend on their entire orbits (right). Ion pick-up in those tori is the main source of plasma in both magnetospheres. *Credit : CICLOPS, NASA, JPL, ESA, NASA/JPL-Caltech/Space Science Institute*

1.2 The magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn

The magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn are characterised by a strong magnetic field and rapid rotation of the plasma, due to the rapid rotation of the planet. They are thus very extended : their magnetopause, the boundary between the magnetic field of the planet and the interplanetary magnetic field, are located, on the dayside, at $45\text{-}100 R_J$ at Jupiter, and $23 R_S$ at Saturn (Gombosi et al. 2009). Both magnetospheres display disks of plasma which extend to the location of their magnetopause.

The magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn differ from each other on various aspects. The magnetic field in the Kronian magnetosphere is very close to a dipolar configuration. On the contrary, the interaction of the Jovian magnetic field with the magnetospheric plasma stretches magnetic field lines radially outward under the effect of strong centrifugal forces and bends them azimuthally. It causes an important departure from a dipolar field and generates a thin magnetodisk configuration beyond the orbits of Io and Europa. Finally, the strong magnetic field of Jupiter ($4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ T, compared to $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ T at Saturn) leads to a significantly more extended magnetosphere.

The production, transport and loss processes in the plasma in both magnetodisks are well summarised by Bagenal and Delamere 2011. The plasma sources are numerous in the Saturn and Jupiter magnetospheres : solar wind, planet, satellites... The dominant source of plasma in both magnetospheres is ionisation from the neutral gas tori produced by their most active moons (Io at Jupiter and Enceladus at Saturn), located in their inner magnetospheres at radial distances of approximately $5.9 R_J$ for Io and $4 R_S$ for Enceladus.

As illustrated in figure 2, the dynamics of the Jovian and Kronian magnetospheres can be understood as a coupling between two tori : the neutral torus surrounding the active moon, which follows a keplerian motion, and an ionised torus, extending from the inner parts of the magnetosphere to the magnetopause, mainly governed by the electrodynamic coupling mediated by the magnetic field of the central planet. The neutral torus produces plasma via photo-ionisation and electron impact ionisation, which is the main source of plasma for the system. This plasma is transported outwards, from the location of the neutral torus to the outer parts of the magnetosphere, where it is ejected through reconnection and plasmoid formation (Bagenal and Delamere 2011). These two magnetospheres can thus be split into three main regions : an inner source region at the neutral torus, a region of outward transport through the ionised torus and a region of plasma ejection and loss into the interplanetary medium. In the present study, we do not intend to model the third region, as it is governed by disk disruptions and non-symmetrical outflow of plasma, which fall beyond the scope of this study, but treat it as an external boundary condition.

Figure 2: A simplified sketch of plasma transport in the magnetospheric systems of Jupiter and Saturn. A neutral torus, present in the inner part of the magnetosphere, acts as a source of plasma and is coupled to a plasma torus through radial transport. The magnetosphere can thus be separated into a source region, a region of radial transport driven by electrodynamic coupling to the planet’s fast rotation, and a loss region, in which the plasma is ejected from the system. All sub-regions of the magnetosphere are coupled to the ionosphere through field-aligned current loops. At high-latitude, field-aligned potentials established between the ionospheric domain and the equator accelerate the electrons and enhance field-aligned currents, leading to the formation of auroras.

1.3 Transport models in the magnetospheres of giant planets

Describing the radial transport of plasma in the magnetospheres of the giant planets has been a long-lasting effort involving observations as well as theoretical modelling and numerical simulations. The theoretical models of the radial transport in rapidly rotating magnetospheres can be separated into two main types.

The first type of models, referred to as *type 1 models* in the following, describes the radial transport of angular momentum throughout the magnetosphere. Such models were initially developed by Hill 1979 and Pontius 1997 to explain the plasma rotation curve observed by the Voyager spacecraft during their fly-bys of the gas giants, and further refined by Cowley and Bunce 2001, Achilleos, Guio, et al. 2010 and Nichols 2011. The radial evolution of angular momentum is computed taking into account the coupling between the plasma disk in the equator plane and the ionosphere of the planet through electric current loops flowing along magnetic field lines (see figure 2). These current loops transfer angular momentum between the ionosphere and the equator via the Lorentz force. Using such a description, Cowley and Bunce 2001 we are able, for instance, to accurately predict the latitudinal distribution of field-aligned currents and the location of the main aurora in the magnetosphere of Jupiter.

In order to focus on the coupling between physical quantities at the equator and in the ionosphere, all such models make strong approximations for the magnetodisk, assuming null pressure and thickness and overlooking the complex two-dimensional geometry of magnetic field lines and plasma distribution in each longitude plane, thus their complex interplay. Interestingly, these models also assume a steady radial outward flow of mass (advection) through the disk, but do not explain how such a flow of matter can be spatially organised without violating the conservation of magnetic flux in this magneto-hydrodynamical flow.

The second type of models, which focuses on an accurate description of radial transport of the plasma content (mass and energy) of the flux tubes in the magnetosphere, is referred to as the *type 2 models* in the following.

These models describe radial transport of flux-tube content based on the flux tube interchange instability, studied for instance by (Ferrière, Zimmer, et al. 2001). In the flux tube interchange instability a denser flux tube located closer to the planet is dragged outward under the influence of the centrifugal force and exchanges with a lighter flux tube located at a larger radius, experiencing a smaller centrifugal force. This instability is similar to the Rayleigh-Taylor instability in neutral fluids, which mixes a denser fluid on top of a lighter fluid under the action of its higher gravitational potential. The reader is invited to the review papers by Achilleos, André, et al. 2015 and Krupp et al. 2004 for a more detailed discussion on the interchange instability in the magnetosphere of gas giants. Multiple evidence of interchange events have been reported by e.g. Bolton et al. 1997, Kivelson et al. 1997 at Jupiter and e.g. Azari et al. 2018, Rymer et al. 2009 at Saturn, supporting the physical accuracy of those models.

This exchange of flux tubes results in a net outward transport of plasma mass and energy in the magnetodisk. Instabilities are usually linked to diffusive transport, and most transport models based on the interchange instability use diffusion equations for the integrated mass and energy content of the tubes (Siscoe and Summers 1981, Saur 2004). However, recent modelling also achieve a good agreement with the data using advection equations (Ng, Delamere, et al. 2018 at Jupiter and Neupane et al. 2021 at Saturn). The use of an advection-diffusion model by Ng, Neupane, et al. 2021 suggests that the transport is more likely to be driven by advection rather than diffusion at larger radii.

Although the type 2 models fully integrate the thickness of the disk and a physical description of its plasma content, they do not take into account the coupling between the ionosphere and the magnetosphere and its influence on the transport of angular momentum and its exchange between ionosphere and plasma disk.

1.4 Objectives of this study

This work aims at developing a mutually consistent description of radial transport of mass, energy and angular momentum in the Jovian and Kronian magnetodisks including their exchanges of angular momentum with the upper atmospheres of these planets. To achieve this goal, we combine type 1 and type 2 models into a self-consistent description of the transport processes in the Jovian and Kronian magnetospheres. Combining the two approaches will provide a comprehensive understanding of both the interaction between the plasma and the magnetic field in the magnetosphere and the coupling between the magnetodisk and the ionosphere. In addition, a combined model can account for all flux tube contents, mass, energy as well as angular momentum. It requires in the first place a better understanding of the physical processes at play, in order to identify the key hypotheses of the two approaches and to link together all their apparently independent results and predictions.

The simultaneous treatment of the cases of Jupiter and Saturn by the same model structure promises very rich outcomes: a model built to apply to both planets should account for a large variety of physical conditions in the parameter space of the system, thus opening to a wide range of applications.

This report is organised as follows. We first identify, in section 2, the key assumptions accounting for both planets and allowing the derivation of a combined approach between angular momentum transport models and mass and energy transport models. Section 2 also presents the fundamental equations on which this derivation is based. From those equations, the equilibrium state of the magnetosphere is derived in section 3 along each magnetic field line, and extended in section 4 to the 2-D equilibrium throughout an entire magnetic longitude plane. In section 5, this equilibrium is then perturbed to compute the radial transport of flux tubes contents, in the framework of the flux tube interchange instability theory. The azimuthal components of the perturbed equations is further studied analysed in section 6 to derive system of equations describing the transport of angular momentum based on the magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling. Our tentative closed set of equations is finally summarised and discussed in section

7.

2 The magnetospheric environment : system, assumptions, equations

2.1 Magnetospheric environment

2.1.1 Notations

In this section, we provide a list of the various quantities and notations used in this work.

The spherical coordinates are (r, θ, ϕ) , and the associated coordinate vectors are $(\mathbf{e}_r, \mathbf{e}_\theta, \mathbf{e}_\phi)$. The cylindrical coordinates are written (R, ϕ, z) , and bore by the vectors $(\mathbf{e}_R, \mathbf{e}_\phi, \mathbf{e}_z)$. Both Euler potential, α and β , are introduced in the next section, together with the local coordinates (α, β, ζ) . For a more detailed explanation of the relations between the local and the spherical coordinates, see section 2.2.

The properties and quantities associated to the magnetosphere, its plasma populations and the ionosphere are defined in table 1.

Planet	
Planet radius	$R_P (R_S, R_J)$
Planet mass	$M_P (M_S, M_J)$
Planet rotation rate	$\Omega_P (\Omega_S, \Omega_J)$
Planet equatorial surface magnetic field strength	$B_P (B_S, B_J)$
Magnetic field	
Magnetic field	\mathbf{B}
Electric field	\mathbf{E}
Rotation associated to the magnetic field	Ω
Cylindrical radius of the magnetic line crossing of the equatorial plane	R_{eq}
Plasma	
Current density	\mathbf{j}
Pressure	P
Mass density	ρ
Number density	n
Velocity	\mathbf{v}
Particle mass, charge number, temperature of species i	m_i, Z_i, T_i
Ionosphere	
Ionospheric distance to the planet rotation axis	R_i
Ionospheric distance to the planet centre	r_i
Ionospheric Pedersen conductivity	σ_P
Ionospheric Pedersen conductance	Σ_P
Rotation rate of the neutral atmosphere	Ω_n
Others	
Proton mass	m_p
Electron mass	m_e
Gravitational constant	G
Gravitational acceleration	g
Rotation rate associated with keplerian motion	$\Omega_K \simeq \sqrt{\frac{GM_P}{R^3}}$

Table 1: Notations. The specific notation for Saturn and Jupiter respectively are provided in parentheses.

2.1.2 Plasma composition

In this section, we give a brief overview of the various observations of plasma populations in the magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn. We use these observations to support a certain number of assumptions made in our further description of their plasma populations.

Saturn In their analysis of the Ion Mass Spectrometer (IMS/CAPS) observations on-board Cassini, which provides measurements of the energy of low energy ions (from 1 to 50.28 keV), Livi et al. 2014 showed that the ion energy spectra measured in the middle-magnetosphere are represented reasonably well by two Maxwellian populations of ions, H^+ and OH^+ (see Figure 3 in their paper). This two-component description can be largely found in the literature up to a $50 R_S$ radius (e.g. Wilson et al. 2008; McAndrews et al. 2009; Dialynas et al. 2018).

Schippers et al. 2008 analysed the electron energy spectra from CAPS/ELS and MIMI/LEMMS instruments from 1 eV to 10 MeV. They showed that these spectra can be very well represented by two populations of electrons. Even though the data were better fitted by two kappa distribution, a description using two Maxwellian distributions for the electrons still agrees quite well with their data, and with the later study of CAPS/ELS data performed by Livi et al. 2014.

Jupiter The plasma composition in the magnetosphere of Jupiter proved to be richer than at Saturn. Kim et al. 2020 accounted for the ions spectra measured by JADE-I on board JUNO, from 10 to 50 R_J and from 10 eV to 46.2 keV, using a total of eight ionic populations. The authors showed that the ion populations are dominated by H^+ , O^+ and S^{2+} with a O^+/S^{2+} number density ratio between 0.5 and 2. Poppe et al. 2018 also emphasise the presence of many ion populations, among which two populations of protons, thermal and energetic, are distinguished.

Scudder et al. 1981 provided evidence of the presence of two electron populations in Voyager I data between 5.5 and 17 R_J in the Jovian magnetosphere. They measured temperatures of 600 eV to 1.2 keV for the so-called "hot" or "warm" population, and temperatures of 6 to 39 eV for the so-called "cold" component.

Based on observations at the two planets, we choose to describe the magnetospheric plasma as a mixture of four populations, two ion and two electron populations. Even though the two-ions approximation does not correspond perfectly well to the ion spectra at Jupiter (Poppe et al. 2018), it still provides a reasonable level of simplification for the present study of global transport processes in these magnetospheres. This approximation is also strongly suggested in the work of Kim et al. 2020 and Huscher et al. 2021.

We differentiate the two ion populations according to their masses, assuming that one population, indexed "l" in the following report, is much lighter than the other one, indexed "h" for "heavy". The lighter population corresponds to protons, and the heavier one corresponds to water ions at Saturn and to a balanced mixture of oxygen and sulphur ions at Jupiter. The two electron populations are discriminated according to their temperature, namely a cold and a hot population, respectively indexed "e,c" and "e,h". Orders of magnitudes are given in table 2 for the properties of each population at Jupiter and Saturn, based on the literature cited here.

Wilson et al. 2008 showed, from the analysis of IMS/CAPS data, that the ion species at Saturn showed some temperature anisotropy with a factor $\frac{T_{\perp}}{T_{\parallel}} \sim 2$ for both species. For the sake of simplifying our equations, we do not take temperature anisotropy into account and consider $T_{i,\perp} = T_{i,\parallel} = T_i$ for all populations.

Parameter	Values at Jupiter	Values at Saturn
Heavy ions		
T_h (eV)	$2 \cdot 10^3 - 7 \cdot 10^4$	$1 \cdot 10^2 - 2 \cdot 10^3$
m_h (kg)	$24 m_H$	$18 m_H$
Z_h	1	1
Light ions		
T_l (eV)	$1 \cdot 10^2 - 3 \cdot 10^4$	$6 - 3 \cdot 10^2$
m_l	m_H	m_H
Z_l	1	1
α	0.2-0.5	0.07-0.2
Cold electrons		
$T_{e,c}$ (eV)		$6 - 4 \cdot 10^2$
$m_{e,c}$ (kg)	m_e	m_e
Z_e	-1	-1
Hot electrons		
$T_{e,h}$ (eV)		$6 \cdot 10^2 - 1 \cdot 10^3$
$m_{e,h}$ (kg)	m_e	m_e
Z_e	-1	-1

Table 2: Typical values of the properties of each population for the cases of Jupiter and Saturn. A population i is characterised by its temperature T_i , particle mass m_i , and charge number Z_i . α is the ratio between the number densities of light and heavy ions at the equator. The ordering is based on the work of Schippers et al. 2008, Wilson et al. 2008 and McAndrews et al. 2009 at Saturn, and Kim et al. 2020 at Jupiter.

2.1.3 Sources of plasma ?

2.2 Local coordinates

The local coordinate system described by Ferrière, Zimmer, et al. 2001 is particularly adapted to the description of quantities and their evolution in a magnetic field. This system writes (α, β, ζ) on orthonormal vectors $(\mathbf{e}_\alpha, \mathbf{e}_\beta, \mathbf{e}_\zeta)$ where :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{B} &= \nabla\alpha \times \nabla\beta \\ \beta &= R_p\phi \\ \nabla\zeta &\parallel \mathbf{B} \end{aligned}$$

Going from the spherical coordinates system to the local coordinates system is possible using the relation :

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathbf{r} &= dr\mathbf{e}_r + rd\theta\mathbf{e}_\theta + r\sin(\theta)d\phi\mathbf{e}_\phi \\ &= h_\alpha d\alpha\mathbf{e}_\alpha + h_\beta d\beta\mathbf{e}_\beta + h_\zeta d\zeta\mathbf{e}_\zeta \end{aligned}$$

According to Ferrière, Zimmer, et al. 2001, $h_\beta = \frac{R}{R_p}$, $B = \|\mathbf{B}\| = \frac{1}{h_\alpha h_\beta}$, and $h_\alpha = \frac{R_p}{BR}$. We additionally write $ds = h_\zeta d\zeta$, with s the curvilinear abscissa.

A last useful set of formula for the present study is that of the surface vectors. The surface vector on a magnetic flux shell writes $d\mathbf{S}_\perp = h_\beta d\beta d\mathbf{e}_\alpha = r\sin(\theta)d\phi d\mathbf{e}_\alpha$. and the surface vector parallel to the magnetic field lines is $d\mathbf{S}_\parallel = h_\alpha h_\beta d\alpha d\beta \mathbf{e}_\zeta = \frac{d\alpha d\beta}{B} \mathbf{e}_\zeta$. The parallel-to-field-lines magnetic flux is then $d\Phi = \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_\parallel = d\alpha d\beta = R_p d\alpha d\phi$. It is conserved along field lines.

2.3 Magnetospheric fundamental equations

We base our derivation on a set of fundamental equations, which we present in the following. The system of interest for our study, comprising the planet and its surroundings inside the magnetopause boundary, can be separated in three main domains, to which different sets of equations apply: the magnetospheric domain, the ionospheric domain, and the high latitude auroral and polar domain, to which a fourth domain corresponding to the planet interior can be added separated in figure 2 by thick dashed lines. All three domains are coupled through currents propagating parallel to the magnetic field. Magnetic field lines are assumed to be frozen into magnetospheric flows and the ionosphere as long as they can be assumed to be perfect conductors.

2.3.1 The magnetosphere

The magnetospheric region correspond to the medium surrounding the planet above a given altitude. It is a collisionless medium, to which the magneto-hydrodynamics equations apply. We write those equations in the planetocentric inertial frame in the following.

To keep the full generality of the problem, we include source terms, corresponding to the pick-up of ions in the neutral cloud surrounding the moons for instance, and loss terms, linked to charge exchanges in the inner and middle magnetosphere. Pick-up is the process through which a neutral particle in the magnetosphere, ionised by irradiation or interaction with other particles, produces an electron and an ion which are then accelerated by the electromagnetic field from a near keplerian motion to the plasma motion. It is a source of mass and thermal energy, with respective source rates $\mathcal{S}_{m,pu}$ and $\mathcal{S}_{q,pu}$, as well as momentum, through the addition of a *pick-up current* in the Lorentz force.

The pick-up process and the generation of the pick-up current are illustrated in figure 3, in the inertial frame of the keplerian neutral particle, orbiting at a rotation rate $\Omega_K \simeq \sqrt{\frac{GM_P}{R^3}}$ around the planet. After ionisation, the newly created pair of ion and electron drifts in the electromagnetic field of the planet with a velocity $\mathbf{v} = \frac{\mathbf{E}' \times \mathbf{B}}{B^2}$ where \mathbf{E}' and \mathbf{B} are the electric and magnetic fields in the local rest frame of the (nearly) keplerian neutral cloud. As they start their drifting motion with an initial acceleration along the direction of the local electrostatic field but in opposite directions due to their opposite charges (see figure 3), they are spatially separated in the direction of the electric field by the sum of their gyro-radii linked to the magnetic field \mathbf{B} . The contribution of an ionisation to the total pick-up current can be written $d\mathbf{j}_{pu} = \frac{(m_i+m_e)}{B^2} \mathbf{E}'$. The total pick-up current is then obtained by noting that the rate of ionised neutral is $\frac{\mathcal{S}_{m,pu}}{m_i+m_e}$, and $\mathbf{j}_{pu} = \frac{\mathcal{S}_{m,pu}}{m_i+m_e} d\mathbf{j}_{pu}$. Setting $\sigma_P = \frac{\mathcal{S}_{m,pu}}{B^2}$ a *pick-up conductivity* allows to write an Ohm's law for the pick-up current :

$$\mathbf{j}_{pu} = \frac{\mathcal{S}_{m,pu}}{B^2} \mathbf{E}' = \sigma_{pu} \mathbf{E}' \quad (1)$$

On the other hand, recombination results in a loss of mass and energy for the plasma, but not of angular momentum, as the ion which has been neutralised do not interact with the electromagnetic field nor the plasma (in collisionless regime).

The conservation of mass is, writing $\mathcal{S}_{m,pu}$ the source of mass due to pick-up of ions, and \mathcal{L}_m , the loss of mass :

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \rho \mathbf{v} = \mathcal{S}_{m,pu} - \mathcal{L}_m \quad (2)$$

In the transport of momentum, pick-up processes result in the addition of a Lorentz-like force due to a pick-up current \mathbf{j}_{pu} in the force balance, as follows :

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) = -\nabla P + \mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{j}_{pu} \times \mathbf{B} + \rho \mathbf{g} \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: Generation of an electric current through the pick-up process. When ionised, a neutral particle produces a pair of ion and electron. Both particles follow a drift motion in the electromagnetic field associated to the referential frame of the neutral. On average, they are spatially separated by the sum of their gyro-radii $R_i + R_e = \frac{m_i v}{eB} + \frac{m_e v}{eB}$, and thus contribute to the total pick-up current by $d\mathbf{j}_{pu} = e(R_i + R_e)$. The total pick-up current is obtained by weighting the contribution of a single pair by the rate of pair creation.

The induction law is written, for perfect magneto-hydrodynamics :

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (4)$$

The transport of energy includes a pick-up heating rate $\mathcal{S}_{q,pu}$ and a loss term \mathcal{L}_q :

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \frac{P}{\rho^\gamma} = \mathcal{S}_{q,pu} - \mathcal{L}_q \quad (5)$$

Completeness of the set of equations is achieved adding state equations for the plasma in the magnetosphere :

Charge neutrality, where the sum is done over all plasma species :

$$\sum_i Z_i e n_i = 0 \quad (6)$$

Perfect gas law applied to each plasma species :

$$P = \sum_i P_i = \sum_i n_i k_B T_i \quad (7)$$

2.3.2 The ionosphere

The second domain is the ionospheric domain, located below a given altitude, in the upper part of the planet's atmosphere where the atmospheric particles are gradually ionised by incoming radiations. The ionisation rate in the ionosphere is very low (10^{-6} to 10^{-2} , Nagy et al. 2009), and thus the upper atmosphere is mainly neutral. The charged particles constituting the ionosphere are in permanent collisional interactions with the neutral atoms and molecules constituting the neutral upper atmosphere, usually referred to as the "thermosphere".

In this region, charged particles transport across magnetic field lines results from a balance between the Lorentz force and collision with neutral particles. At the bottom of the ionosphere, collisions dominate, and ions and electrons follow the dynamics of the neutral gas. In the upper part of the ionosphere,

where the collision rate is smaller, ions and electrons decouple from neutral particles and follow their own dynamics, i.e. the frozen-in $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ drift motion of magnetic field lines. The rotation vector of magnetic field lines and tubes in the upper part of the ionosphere $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is thus different from the rotation vector of the planet $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_P$, first due to the proper motion of the upper atmosphere, which can strongly depart from the motion of the interior of the planet, and second, due to this drifting of particles.

The net electric current produced by the different dynamic behaviours of ions and electrons can be generally described by an ionospheric Ohm's law, which write, in the planetocentric inertial frame :

$$\mathbf{j} = \bar{\bar{\sigma}}(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{\bar{\sigma}} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_P & \sigma_H \\ \sigma_H & \sigma_P \end{bmatrix}$ is the conductivity tensor, expressed in the local frame $(\mathbf{e}_\alpha, \mathbf{e}_\beta)$ with the Pedersen and Hall conductivity respectively written σ_P and σ_H . In the previous expression, $\mathbf{v}(\alpha, s)$ is the sum of the velocity of corotation with the planet $\mathbf{v}_{cor} = \boldsymbol{\Omega}_P \times \mathbf{r} = R\boldsymbol{\Omega}_P \mathbf{e}_\beta$ and the proper velocity of the neutral wind in the corotating frame \mathbf{v}_n , which can present an azimuthal component $v_{n,\beta}$ as well as a meridian component $v_{n,\alpha}$ ($v_{n,\parallel}$ playing no role in Ohm's law).

In the most general case, we will write the Ohm's law in terms of a relation between the field aligned currents and the ionospheric electric potential, taken in the inertial planetocentric frame, Φ_i such that $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\Phi$. Assuming a thin ionosphere, the curvature of the magnetic field lines through the ionosphere can be neglected, and the field lines can be approximated as straight lines in the ionosphere (see figure 4). In an axisymmetric configuration, $E_\beta = 0$ and the meridional current writes :

$$j_\alpha = \sigma_P(\Omega R B - \frac{1}{h_\alpha} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \alpha}) + \sigma_P B v_{n,\beta} - \sigma_H B v_{n,\alpha} \quad (9)$$

In the case of a thin ionosphere, the electrostatic potential, magnetic field and ionospheric distance to the rotation axis are assumed constant over the ionosphere height, and their ionospheric values are noted with the index i . The expression of the integrated perpendicular ionospheric currents along a field line is thus :

$$J_{i\alpha} = \int_s j_\alpha ds d\phi = \left(\Omega_P R_P - \frac{\partial \Phi_i}{\partial \alpha} \right) \frac{\Sigma_P R_i B_i}{R_P \sin(I)} + B_i \int_0^{s_i} \sigma_P v_{n,\beta} ds - B_i \int_0^{s_i} \sigma_H v_{n,\alpha} ds \quad (10)$$

In the above, $\Sigma_P = \int_0^{s_i} \sigma_P \sin(I) ds$ is the vertically integrated ionospheric Pedersen conductance. Wang et al. 2021 show, based on observations and modelling, that the contribution of the neutral wind will be neglected in the main aurora. We will hence make this approximation in our derivations.

Assuming rigid corotation of field lines, it is useful to express the electric field, and thus the field-aligned currents as a function of the rotation rate of the field line. The drift velocity of the ions in the planetocentric frame is $\mathbf{v}_d = \frac{\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}}{B^2}$. On the other hand, this velocity corresponds to the rotation of the field lines in this frame and can be written $\mathbf{v}_d = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}$, leading to the following expression for the electric field :

$$\mathbf{E} = -(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) \times \mathbf{B} = -\Omega R B \mathbf{e}_\alpha \quad (11)$$

2.3.3 High latitude auroral and polar field lines

The magnetospheric plasma is coupled to the upper atmosphere of the planet through electrical currents, born by electrons moving along field lines. At high latitudes, where the density of plasma is faint and localised space charges appear, the fluid description of the electrons motion is not possible. The field lines in this region depart from perfect conductors, and some level of decoupling can then appear between the magnetosdisk and its ionospheric counterpart.

Figure 4: The ionosphere is assumed thin enough to neglect the curvature of the field lines through it. Under this approximation, we define the inclination I of the field line as the angle between e_ζ and e_θ .

The high latitude field lines are characterised by the field-aligned potential drop written Φ_{\parallel} in the planetocentric inertial frame, and defined as the difference between the ionospheric and the equatorial electrostatic potentials along a given field line :

$$\Phi_{\parallel} = \Phi_i - \Phi_{eq} \quad (12)$$

In the following, the potential drop is assumed to set in a very confined domain at high latitude such that field lines can be approximated as perfect conductors rigidly rotating through the magnetodisk, and their rotation rate be non-ambiguously defined in the magnetospheric domain.

The dynamical processes taking place in the high latitude polar domain have been investigated by e.g. Knight 1973 under a kinetic description of the movement of electrons and their behaviour under magnetic mirror forces. Under a certain number of simplifying assumptions, meaning those of a steady state, two Maxwellian plasma populations, monotonic electrostatic potential and density along field lines and negligible gravitational and centrifugal forces, Knight 1973 derived an expression of the field-aligned current at high latitude, as a function of the field-aligned potential drop Φ_{\parallel} :

$$j_{\parallel,i} = eB_i \left(n_{e,i} \sqrt{\frac{k_B T_{e,i}}{2\pi m_e}} g(\Phi_{\parallel}, T_{e,i}) - n_{e,eq} \sqrt{\frac{k_B T_{e,eq}}{2\pi m_e}} g(\Phi_{\parallel}, T_{e,eq}) \exp\left(\frac{e\Phi_{\parallel}}{k_B T_{e,eq}}\right) \right) \quad (13)$$

where

$$g(\Phi_{\parallel}, T) = \frac{1}{B_{eq}} \left(\exp\left(\frac{-e\Phi_{\parallel}}{k_B T}\right) - \frac{B_i - B_{eq}}{B_i} \exp\left(\frac{-e\Phi_{\parallel}}{k_B T} \frac{B_i}{B_i - B_{eq}}\right) \right)$$

where n_e and T_e and the electronic density and temperature, and indices eq and i refer to equatorial and ionospheric quantities respectively.

More recently, Ray, Su, et al. 2009 derived an new current-voltage relation, taking into account the effects of the centrifugal potential and non-monotonic behaviours along the field lines :

$$j_{\parallel,ik} = j_x + j_x(R_x - 1) \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{e\Phi_{\parallel k}}{T_x(R_x - 1)}\right) \right), \quad k = n \text{ or } s \quad (14)$$

where j_x , T_x and R_x are the thermal current, the electronic temperature and the mirror ratio at the location of the gravitational+centrifugal potential minimum. The thermal current writes $j_x = en_x \sqrt{\frac{T_x}{2\pi m_e}}$,

with n_x the electronic density at the same location. Typical values of those parameters are given by Ray, Ergun, et al. 2010. As they take into account the rotation of field lines, the result of Ray, Su, et al. 2009 seems more adapted to the magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn. In the following, we will refer to equation 14 as the *current-voltage relation*, which we will write $j_{\parallel} = K(\Phi_{\parallel})$.

2.3.4 Averaged and perturbed states

From equations 2 to 7, global transport equations are derived using the quasi-linear theory. In this approach, all quantities A are separated between an averaged term at order 0, $A_0 = \langle A \rangle$, and a first-order perturbation of null mean value, $\delta A = A - A_0$. Based on the axisymmetry of the system, we define averages as azimuthal averages over 2π . They correspond to the equilibrium state of the magnetosphere. Their transport is driven by second order perturbations, and is computed by averaging transport equations (2 to 7), yielding a relation between averaged 0^{th} -order term and second-order perturbations. Third-order and higher-order terms are neglected as well as the contribution of the magnetic field perturbations.

Focusing first on the magnetospheric equilibrium state, the equations are written in sections 3 and 4, keeping only the average quantities at order 0. The perturbations must then be taken into account at second order for the description of the transport processes through the disk in sections 5 and 6.

3 Static equilibrium along field lines

We start our study by deriving the equilibrium configuration along field lines. This is done by projecting equations 2 to 7 onto \mathbf{e}_{ζ} to derive the distribution of plasma species along field lines in the magnetosphere (section 3.1). In sections 3.2.3 and 3.2.4, under some simplifying assumptions, we establish approximate expressions for these distributions in the form of an exponential variation of the densities with distance to the rotation axis. This exponential variation is characterised by a radial scale height independent of the geometry of field lines. We finally show some applications of our analytical results to the case of Jupiter and Saturn in section 3.3.

3.1 General equations

Our derivation is based on the equilibrium formulation of the conservation of momentum (equation 3) applied to each species in the absence of plasma flow, and projected along the magnetic field lines. In the equilibrium state, all perturbations are neglected, as well as pick-up sources and loss terms. We write the conservation of momentum in the frame rotating at a rate Ω corresponding to the motion of ions and the rotation of the field lines :

$$\mathbf{0} = -\frac{\partial P_{i0}}{\partial s} - m_i n_{i0} \frac{\partial \Psi_g}{\partial s} \quad (15)$$

In the above expression, we introduced $\Psi_g = -\frac{\Omega^2 R^2}{2} - \frac{GM_p}{r}$, the sum of the centrifugal and gravitational potentials (where R_{eq} is the radius at which the given field line crosses the equatorial plane). Both potentials equate at a specific equatorial distance from the planet rotation axis equal to $R_{eq} = 2.4R_S$ at Saturn and $R_{eq} = 2.9R_J$ at Jupiter, corresponding to the planeto-synchronous orbit. Below this radius, the gravitational potential dominates in the equation, and above, the centrifugal potential is dominant. As this study focuses on the plasma disk, located beyond the Io and Enceladus tori, at respectively $5.9R_J$ and $4R_S$ in the Jovian and Kronian magnetospheres, the gravitational potential can therefore be neglected. Equation 15 is a system of four equations with five variables, which we close with the plasma quasi-neutrality relation (equation 6).

3.2 General expression for the distribution of ions along field lines

3.2.1 Global equations

Summing equations 15 over all components i first allows to recover the barotropic equilibrium :

$$\frac{\partial P_0}{\partial s} = -\rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi_g}{\partial s} \quad (16)$$

Using the perfect gas law (equation 7) in equation 15 and the conservation of individual temperatures along field lines, predicted by Liouville's theorem (Maurice et al. 1997), the variation of n_{i0} along field lines writes as follows :

$$\frac{\partial n_{i0}}{\partial s} = \left(\frac{Z_i e}{kT_i} E_{0\parallel} + \frac{m_i}{kT_i} \frac{\partial \Psi_g}{\partial s} \right) n_{i0} \quad (17)$$

Combining the above with equation 6 finally results in an equation for the parallel electric field :

$$\left(\sum_i \frac{n_{i0} Z_i^2}{kT_i} \right) e E_{0\parallel} = - \left(\sum_i \frac{Z_i m_i n_{i0}}{kT_i} \right) \frac{\partial \Psi_g}{\partial s} \quad (18)$$

We recover the results of Maurice et al. 1997 in the case of isotropic Maxwellian distributions (see equations (8) and (11) in their paper). In the following sections, we study analytical expressions for the distribution of ions along field lines from equations 17 and 18 in a few limit cases. The results derived here will be useful to interpret the transport equations established later in this report.

3.2.2 Case of a single ionic species

Starting from equations 17 and 18, we first study the simplified case of a single ionic species (m_i, Z_i, n_{i0}, T_i) at equilibrium with an electronic species ($m_e, Z_e = -1, n_{e0}, T_e$). In such a case, the number densities vanish from equation 18 and the parallel electric field can be expressed in terms of the potential Ψ_g , the masses and temperatures of both populations :

$$e E_{0\parallel} = - \frac{m_i k T_e}{Z_i k T_e + k T_i} \frac{\partial \Psi_g}{\partial s} \quad (19)$$

Using equation 19 and equation 17 for the ions and neglecting the electron mass then gives the distribution of ions at all points along the field line:

$$n_{i0} = n_{i0,eq} \exp \left(- \frac{m_i}{Z_i k T_e + k T_i} (\Psi_g(s) - \Psi_{g,eq}) \right) \quad (20)$$

where $n_{h0,eq}$ and $\Psi_{g,eq}$ are the values of the number density and the potential at the location where the field line crosses the equator plane. Equation 20 provides the dependence of the scale height of the plasma sheet on the ionic and electronic parameters. As Ψ_g does not depend on the nature of the populations, the scale height of a given field line varies as $\frac{Z_i k T_e + k T_i}{m_i}$. Hence, the heavier the ions and the colder the ions or the electrons, the thinner the plasma sheet. This is strongly reminiscent of the hydrostatic equilibrium in disks. Equation 19 also shows that the electric field is higher for more massive ions.

3.2.3 Case of two ionic populations : distribution of the dominant species

In the case of four populations the distribution of heavy ions near the equator and the distribution of light ions far from the equator can be fairly well described using the two-component approximation described in section 3.2.2.

Heavy ions near the equator Based on the observations available at Jupiter and Saturn (e.g. Schippers et al. 2008) and the discussion of Maurice et al. 1997 on the plasma equilibrium along field lines, we assume here that the heavy-ion population and one electron population are dominant in the vicinity of the equator. This leads to a two-component equilibrium between the heavy ions and one population of electrons with temperature T_e (which could be the cold population in the inner disk, as shown by Schippers et al. 2008) :

$$n_{h0} = n_{h0,eq} \exp\left(-\frac{m_h}{Z_h k T_e + k T_h} (\Psi_g(s) - \Psi_{g,eq})\right), \text{ s small} \quad (21)$$

It is then possible to derive the radial scale height (as illustrated in figure 5) associated with the distribution given by the above equation 21 making two additional assumption, neglecting the gravitational potential, and assuming that ions are confined near the equator, hence that $h_R = R_{eq} - R \ll R_{eq}$. Under those assumptions, $\Psi_g - \Psi_{g,eq} \simeq \frac{\Omega^2}{2} (R_{eq}^2 - R^2) \simeq \Omega^2 R_{eq} h_R$, the heavy ions density decreases exponentially with h_R along the field line, with a radial scale height (illustrated in figure 5)

$$H_{h,1} = \frac{Z_h k T_e + k T_h}{m_h \Omega^2 R_{eq}} \quad (22)$$

We recover the dependence of the radial scale height on the plasma parameters discussed at the end of section 3.2.2.

Figure 5: We describe the distribution of ions along the magnetic field lines in terms of the radial scale height H , which is independent of the geometry of the magnetic field lines. From H , the latitudinal or vertical scale height of the plasma disk can then be derived for any topology of the magnetic field, as shown by the dashed and dotted arrows, corresponding to the dashed and dotted field lines. H depends on the temperature of ions and electrons, the ions mass, and the radius R_{eq} at which the field line crosses the equator plane (see equations 22, 24, 26 and 28).

Light ions far from equator On the other hand, as light ions are more spread along the field line than heavy ions, they are expected to dominate far from the equator (see equation 20 and the discussion of Maurice et al. 1997). The two-components result can thus be applied to describe the distribution of

light ions away from the equator :

$$n_{l0} = n_{l0}^* \exp\left(-\frac{m_l}{Z_l k T_e + k T_l} (\Psi_g(s) - \Psi_{g,eq})\right), \text{ s large} \quad (23)$$

where n_{l0}^* is a constant, and T_e is the temperature of the dominating electronic species, either the cold or the hot population depending on the radial location in the disk.

We can also make the two approximations used to compute the scale height of the heavy ions distribution near the equator to simplify equation 23 and derive an associated radial scale height. As equation 23 characterise the tail of the distributions along the field line, this requires that the decrease of the density be rapid, so that the tail of the distribution still falls in the vicinity of the equator ($h \ll R_{eq}$). The analogy between equations 21 and 23 then allows to write the radial scale height for the tail distribution of light ions as :

$$H_{l,2} = \frac{Z_l k T_e + k T_l}{m_l \Omega^2 R_{eq}} \quad (24)$$

3.2.4 Case of two ionic populations : distribution of the minor species

Light ions near the equator In the vicinity of the equatorial plane, the electric field is dominated by the distribution of heavy ions (see equation 19 applied to heavy ions). The light ions experience this strong electric field which drives them away from the equator, and distribute, near the equator, as :

$$n_{l0} = n_{l0,eq} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{k T_l} \left(m_l - \frac{m_h k T_e Z_l}{Z_h k T_e + k T_h}\right) (\Psi_g - \Psi_{g,eq})\right), \text{ s small} \quad (25)$$

In the above, Ψ_g increases with the curvilinear abscissa s , and $m_l < \frac{m_h k T_e Z_l}{Z_h k T_e + k T_h}$, hence the density of light ions increases along the field line. As discussed by Maurice et al. 1997, the light ions are then depleted at the equator, their density shows a maximum value slightly above the disk of heavy ions, and then decreases along the field line away from the equator, less rapidly than the density of heavy ions (see section 3.2.3) : they "float" above the plasma sheet.

We confirm the above by computing the radial scale height associated to the distribution of light ions near the equator, as was done in section 3.2.3. The distribution function rises exponentially along the field line as $n_{l0} = n_{l0,eq} \exp\left(\frac{h R}{H_{l,1}}\right)$ on a radial scale height :

$$H_{l,1} = \frac{k T_l}{\Omega^2 R_{eq} \left(\frac{m_h k T_e Z_l}{Z_h k T_e + k T_h} - m_l\right)} \quad (26)$$

Heavy ions far from the equator Far from the equator, the situation is reversed : the light ions dominate the total density. Equation 25 applies, switching the roles of light and heavy ions :

$$n_{h0} = n_{h0}^* \exp\left(-\frac{1}{k T_h} \left(m_h - \frac{m_l k T_e Z_h}{Z_l k T_e + k T_l}\right) (\Psi_g(s) - \Psi_{g,eq})\right), \text{ s large} \quad (27)$$

where n_{h0}^* is a constant. As $m_h \gg m_l$, and $Z_h \simeq Z_l$, $\frac{m_l k T_e Z_h}{Z_l k T_e + k T_l} \lesssim m_l < m_h$, thus yielding a decreasing number density for the heavy ions along the field line far from the equator. Making the near-equator assumption, yields an exponential decrease of the heavy ions' density with a scale height :

$$H_{h,2} = -\frac{k T_h}{\Omega^2 R_{eq} \left(m_h - \frac{m_l k T_e Z_h}{Z_l k T_e + k T_l}\right)} \quad (28)$$

It is interesting to compare the decreasing scale heights of heavy ion in the core and tail parts of their distribution along field lines. Assuming that all species have approximately the same temperature T and that $Z_l = Z_h = 1$, equations 22 and 28 give :

$$H_{h,2} \sim \frac{kT}{m_h \Omega^2 R_{eq}} \sim \frac{1}{2} H_{h,1}$$

This example illustrates how the heavy ions' density decreases faster far from the equator, where they experience the electric field of light ions, than near the equator, where they dominate. If temperatures are not equal, the analysis is much more complex. However, if they have comparable orders of magnitude, it is thus reasonable to hypothesise that the density drop of heavy ions is still stronger far from the equator.

3.3 Numerical results

In order to compare our analytical approximation to the complete numerical integration of equations 17 and 18, we plot the resulting profiles in the situation corresponding to table 3.

Parameter	Value at Jupiter	Value at Saturn
Electrons		
$T_{e,c}$ (eV)	30	10
$T_{e,h}$ (eV)	10^3	$2 \cdot 10^3$
$\frac{n_{e,w0,eq}}{n_{e,c0,eq}}$	0.1	0.05
Ions		
T_l (eV)	500	30
T_h (eV)	$5 \cdot 10^3$	200
m_l (kg)	$m_p = 1.62 \cdot 10^{-27}$	m_p
m_h (kg)	$24 m_p$	$16 m_p$
Z_l	1	1
Z_h	1	1
$\frac{n_{l0,eq}}{n_{h0,eq}}$	0.25	0.2
Ω (rad.s $^{-1}$)	$\Omega_J = 1.76 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.6 \Omega_S = 9.84 \cdot 10^{-5}$
R_p (m)	$6.9 \cdot 10^7$	$6.0 \cdot 10^7$
M_p (kg)	$1.9 \cdot 10^{27}$	$5.7 \cdot 10^{26}$
B_p (T)	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Table 3: Parameters values for the case of Jupiter (Wilson et al. 2008, Schippers et al. 2008 and Kane et al. 2020) and Saturn (Kim et al. 2020, Scudder et al. 1981) at 10 planetary radii.

We assume a dipolar magnetic field configuration and choose parameters values based on the literature at $10 R_p$. All numerical values are given in table 3.

At Saturn, light ions are modelled as protons, and heavy ions as water ions of mass $m_h = 18m_p$. Wilson et al. 2008 measured temperatures of the order 30 eV and 200 eV respectively for the light and heavy ions at $10 R_S$. In addition, based on their measurement of ionic number density, we assume a light-to-heavy ions ratio at the equator of approximately 0.2. According to the same study, the electronic temperatures are approximately 2 keV and 10 eV at the same location. In addition, Schippers et al. 2008 show that the warm-to-cold electron density fraction is approximately 0.05. Finally, based on the study of Kane et al. 2020, we assume a rotation rate $\Omega \sim 0.6\Omega_S$.

At Jupiter, light ions are protons and heavy ions are taken as a mixture of oxygen and sulfur with a density ratio of 1, yielding $m_h = 24m_p$. Following the results from Kim et al. 2020, we assume temperatures of 500 eV and 5 keV at $10 R_J$ for the light and heavy ions respectively. The light-to-heavy

density ratio at the equator is taken to be 0.25, based on the authors' density measurements near the equator. In addition, their derivation of the azimuthal plasma speed suggests full corotation at $10 R_J$. Scudder et al. 1981 reported electronic temperatures measured by Voyager/PLS of approximately 30 eV and 1 keV respectively for the cold and warm electron populations between 7.8 and $17 R_J$. They measure a density ratio between the warm and the cold electronic population at $8.9 R_J$ of approximately 0.1.

The approximated analytical distribution of light and heavy ions given by equations 21, 23, 25 and 27 are illustrated by the dotted lines in figure 6 and compared to the results from the numerical integration of equations 17 and 18. The approximate profiles are fairly close to the numerical solutions for both limit cases and both species. Contrary to the results in the previous section, the light ions' distribution does not show a clear depletion near the equator at $10 R_P$. This could be explained by their rather low temperature in both Jupiter and Saturn cases, which limits the validity of our analysis. However, we see in figure 6 that the flat behaviour of the light ions' distribution near the equator is still rather well reproduced by our approximated profiles.

Figure 5.A of
Huscher et al. 2021

Figure 6: *Top panel* : Latitudinal distribution of the various populations along field lines using plasma properties given in table 3, normalized to the total ion number density. The solid lines are obtained through a numerical integration of equations 17 and 18 for the case of four isotropic populations. The dashed lines are analytical approximations in the near-equator limit (equations 21 and 25), and the dotted lines are analytical approximations in the far-from-equator limit (equations 23 and 27). *Bottom panel* : The flatter distribution of light ions (protons) predicted by our results reproduces very well the behaviour observed by e.g. Huscher et al. 2021 with the Juno-JADE instrument at Jupiter.

3.4 Summary

Projecting equations 2 to 7 parallel to the field lines allowed to write equations for the distribution of plasma in the magnetosphere in the equilibrium state for a given magnetic field topology. We were able to solve those equations numerically for a set of parameters corresponding to the Jovian and Kronian magnetospheric conditions at 10 planetary radii, and a dipolar magnetic field. Although the magnetic field at Saturn is fairly dipolar in most parts of the magnetosphere, it is not the case at Jupiter. However, the extension of our numerical resolution is straightforward to any magnetic field topology for which ds can be expressed as an analytical function of dr and $d\theta$.

Analysing equations 17 and 18 in various regimes lead to approximated analytical expressions for the distribution of ions along field lines, which compared successfully to the numerical solutions. A by-product of this analysis is the derivation of radial scale heights in the various regimes, which will be useful for a dimension analysis of the equilibrium state equations as well as the transport equations derived in the following.

4 Static equilibrium in the meridian plane

We complete our description of the equilibrium state by deriving the magnetic field topology, given the plasma properties in the equator plane. Combined with equations 17 and 18, the resulting equation will allow for a consistent description of the equilibrium between the plasma and the magnetic field, given the properties of the magnetosphere at the equator.

Caudal 1986 studied the equilibrium between magnetic field and plasma in the magnetospheres of gas giants. They derived a Grad-Shafranov equation for the evolution of the magnetic potential α along field lines, given a distribution of plasma species in the equatorial plasma disk. A main assumption in his derivation is that the plasma is made of a single ionic species, at thermal equilibrium with a single electronic population. This hypothesis is highly arguable in the magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn, which many studies describe with the help of at least two ionic species and two electronic species with different temperatures (see discussions in sections 2.1.2 and 3.3). Achilleos, Guio, et al. 2010 and Nichols 2011 extended the result from Caudal 1986 with the help of a two-plasma assumptions : two independent ionic species, each in thermal equilibrium with their own electronic species.

In the following, we show how the derivation of Caudal 1986 applies to our system, described by the set of equations given in section 2 and constrained by the assumptions listed in the same section. We recover the result from Achilleos, Guio, et al. 2010 under a two-plasma approximation.

4.1 General equation

We study the equilibrium state of the momentum conservation in the meridian plane :

$$\mathbf{j}_0 \times \mathbf{B}_0 = \nabla P_0 - \rho_0 R \Omega^2 \mathbf{e}_R \quad (29)$$

We write the magnetic field in terms of the Euler potential and use the relation $\mathbf{j}_0 = \nabla \times \mathbf{B}_0$ to give the following expression of the Lorentz force :

$$\mathbf{j}_0 \times \mathbf{B}_0 = -\frac{R_P^2}{R^2 \mu_0} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1 - \mu^2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial \mu^2} \right) \nabla \alpha_0$$

where $\mu = \cos(\theta)$

As each population is assumed to follow the perfect gas law (equation 7), the plasma density then writes, summing over all species k , $\rho_0 = \sum \frac{R P_{k0} m_k}{k_B T_k}$, and equation 29 becomes :

$$\mathbf{j}_0 \times \mathbf{B}_0 = \sum_k \left(\nabla P_{k0} - \frac{R P_{k0}}{l_k^2} \mathbf{e}_R \right)$$

where $l_k^2 = \frac{k_B T_k}{\Omega^2 m_k}$.

Following Caudal 1986, we then introduce $\Pi_{k0} = \exp\left(-\frac{R^2}{2l_k^2}\right) P_{k0}$, yielding :

$$-\frac{R_P^2}{\mu_0 R^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1 - \mu^2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial \mu^2} \right) \nabla \alpha_0 = \sum_k \left(\nabla \Pi_{k0} + \frac{R^2}{2} \Pi_{k0} \frac{\partial l_k^{-2}}{\partial \alpha_0} \nabla \alpha_0 \right) \exp\left(\frac{R^2}{2l_k^2}\right) \quad (30)$$

4.2 Case of a single ionic species

In the case of a single ionic species, at thermal equilibrium with an electronic population, equation 30 becomes (Caudal 1986) :

$$-\frac{R_P^2}{\mu_0 R^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1 - \mu^2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial \mu^2} \right) \nabla \alpha_0 = \left(\nabla \Pi_0 + \frac{R^2}{2} \Pi_0 \frac{\partial l^{-2}}{\partial \alpha_0} \nabla \alpha_0 \right) \exp\left(\frac{R^2}{2l^2}\right)$$

having $l^2 = \frac{(Z+1)k_B T}{\Omega^2 m}$, Z and m the charge number and the mass of the ions, and P_0 the total plasma pressure (Π_0 being defined as above from P_0 and l). It then appears that $\nabla \Pi_0 \parallel \nabla \alpha_0$. Hence Π_0 is constant along field lines and the equation can be simplified as done by Caudal 1986:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1 - \mu^2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial \mu^2} = -\mu_0 \frac{R^2}{R_P^2} \left(\frac{\partial P_{0eq}}{\partial \alpha_0} + \frac{P_{0eq} R_P}{l^2 B_{0\theta,eq}} \right) \exp\left(\frac{R^2 - R_{eq}^2}{2l^2}\right) \quad (31)$$

The right hand side acts as a source of magnetic flux, and is thus referred to as the *source function*.

4.3 Case of two ionic populations

Following Achilleos, Guio, et al. 2010, we extend the work of Caudal 1986 to the case of two ionic species under the two-plasma approximation. We therefore consider two independent ionic species, each in thermal equilibrium with their own electronic species. In such a case, the momentum equilibrium can be written independently for both plasma. The source function is then the sum of the individual source functions, and equation 30 becomes :

$$\frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1 - \mu^2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \alpha_0}{\partial \mu^2} = -\mu_0 \frac{R^2}{R_P^2} \sum_{k=l \text{ or } h} \left(\frac{\partial P_{k0,eq}}{\partial \alpha} + \frac{P_{k0,eq} R_P}{l_k^2 B_{0\theta,eq}} \right) \exp\left(\frac{R^2 - R_{eq}^2}{2l_k^2}\right) \quad (32)$$

4.4 Summary

Studying the meridian component of equation 3 allowed to derive the dependence of the magnetic field on the plasma parameters at the equator. We recovered the results from Achilleos, Guio, et al. 2010 and Nichols 2011 in the form of a Grad-Shafranov equation for the magnetic potential α_0 . From this result, equation 17 and 18 can then be used to compute the distribution of the plasma in the magnetosphere and thus achieve a complete description of the equilibrium state of the magnetosphere, given its properties in the equator plane. Those properties will be derived in section 5, through quasi-static perturbations of the equilibrium state to obtain a self-consistent model of transport in the magnetosphere.

5 Transport processes

Having derived a full description of the equilibrium state of the magnetosphere based on an analysis of the force balance given by the equation of conservation of momentum in the steady state (equation 3), we now study small departures from the equilibrium and how they can drive radial transport of integrated

flux tube quantities in the magnetosphere. In this section, we aim at deriving transport equation for the angular momentum, mass and energy contents of flux tubes based on the equations of conservation of momentum, mass and energy respectively, which we recall here :

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \rho \mathbf{v} = \mathcal{S}_{m,pu} - \mathcal{L}_{m,r} \quad (2)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) = -\nabla P + \mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{j}_{pu} \times \mathbf{B} + \rho \mathbf{g} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \frac{P}{\rho^\gamma} = \mathcal{S}_{q,pu} - \mathcal{L}_{q,r} \quad (5)$$

In order to effectively describe the transport of the total mass, energy and angular momentum contents of flux tubes in the magnetosphere, the above equations are integrated along flux tubes, resulting in transport equations for the integrated quantities.

Magnetospheric transport processes of two different nature have been studied in the literature. Approaches based on advective transport, derived for instance by Ng, Delamere, et al. 2018 and Ng, Neupane, et al. 2021, require a net outflow of mass in the disk, and thus a breakdown of the axisymmetry of the disk which is not compatible with our framework. As shown by Ng, Neupane, et al. 2021, advection becomes dominant in the outer parts of the rotating disk. In those regions, the disk shows strong departure from axisymmetry ; the transport of plasma is there described for instance by the Vasyliunas cycle (Vasyliunas 1983), which allows to explain the loss of plasma in the magnetotail. In the inner and middle parts of the magnetosphere, a description of the plasma outflow conserving axisymmetry as well as magnetic flux, as required by our framework, can only be achieved through diffusive models, based on instability processes occurring at small scales. A very good candidate for such a process is the flux tube interchange instability. As the flux tube density decreases radially in the magnetosdisk, it is indeed nowhere stable under the flux tube interchange instability criterion. In the absence of sources and losses, axisymmetrical transport conserves all three integral quantities : the total mass, energy and angular momentum of flux tubes.

Therefore, in the following, we write conservation equations for the total mass and energy contents of flux tubes and show how both translate in diffusion equations. To do so, we apply a quasi-linear treatment, separating all quantities into an averaged term (indexed 0) and a first-order perturbation of null mean value (noted δ). The average quantities follow the equations derived in sections 3 and 4. Their transport is computed by averaging transport equations, yielding a relation between 0th and second order terms. The derivation of diffusion equations for the mass and the energy contents of flux tubes is shown in sections 5.1 and 5.2.

The transport of angular momentum requires a slightly different approach as, as shown in section 5.3, not only is it driven by the exchange of flux tubes in the magnetosphere, but it is also linked to the coupling between the disk and the planet ionosphere through field-aligned current loops.

5.1 Transport of mass

We first study the transport of the total mass content of flux tubes in the magnetosphere, aiming at the derivation of a diffusion equation for the integrated mass content. However, before getting into the complex formalism of quasi-linear theory and diffusion processes, a first simple analysis of the MHD conservation of mass (equation 2) provides a quantity which will be very useful in the following, naming the total mass outflow through a given flux shell $\dot{M} = - \int_s 2\pi R \langle \rho v_\alpha \rangle ds$. Integrating the equation of equation 2 over the entire volume inside a flux shell leads to :

$$\frac{DM_{int}}{D\alpha} - \int_s 2\pi R \langle \rho v_\alpha \rangle ds = 2\pi R_P \int_\alpha \int_s (\mathcal{S}_{m,pu} - \mathcal{L}_m) \frac{ds}{B} d\alpha$$

where M_{int} is the total mass of plasma located inside the given flux shell, and $\int_s 2\pi R \langle \rho v_\alpha \rangle ds = -\dot{M}$. We write $\overline{\mathcal{F}}_{m,pu} = \int_s \mathcal{F}_{m,pu} \frac{ds}{B}$ and $\overline{\mathcal{L}}_m = \int_s \mathcal{L}_m \frac{ds}{B}$ respectively the total source and loss of mass of a flux tube, per unit magnetic flux. The total source and loss of plasma on a flux shell then write $2\pi R_P \overline{\mathcal{F}}_{m,pu}$ and $2\pi R_P \overline{\mathcal{L}}_m$ and the mass outflow through a given flux shell writes, in the steady state :

$$\dot{M}(\alpha) = \int_\alpha^{\alpha_0} \overline{\mathcal{F}}_{m,pu} d\alpha - \int_\alpha^{\alpha_0} \overline{\mathcal{L}}_m d\alpha \quad (33)$$

where the integral is performed from the flux shell α to the innermost regions α_0 of the magnetosphere where sources and losses are assumed to be zero. Equation 33 does not depend on the nature of the transport processes, it is only valid in the steady-state and corresponds to the conservation of the total mass in the volume defined by the given flux shell. It will be useful for simple applications of our model to Jupiter and Saturn (section 6).

Equation 33 is not sufficient for a complete description of the transport of mass in our framework. Our model indeed require the derivation of the equatorial distribution of plasma, for instance to compute the meridian distribution of plasma along field lines and the disk height in section 3. In addition, we aim at taking into account the temporal variability of the magnetosphere to some extent. In the following, we thus derive a full diffusion equation, starting from the conservation of the total flux tube mass, with the help of the quasi-linear theory.

The integrated mass writes in the case of a single plasma species of particle mass m and total particle number $N = \int n \frac{ds}{B}$ as

$$M = \int \rho \frac{ds}{B} = mN \quad (34)$$

The conservation of the magnetic flux by the interchange instability driven transport yields an incompressibility condition for the two dimensional flow : $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = \nabla \cdot \delta \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0}$. The conservation of the mass content of flux tube translates in a conservation equations in the two-dimensional (α, β) plane :

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (M \mathbf{v}) = \overline{\mathcal{F}}_{m,pu} - \overline{\mathcal{L}}_m \quad (35)$$

In the above, the source and loss terms correspond to those defined in equation 2 integrated over the flux tube. Splitting all quantities between averaged and perturbed values, and averaging equation 35 over 2π yields (neglecting three and higher order terms) :

$$\frac{\partial M_0}{\partial t} + B_0 \frac{\partial (h_\beta \langle \delta v_\alpha \delta M \rangle)}{\partial \alpha} = \overline{\mathcal{F}}_{m,pu} - \overline{\mathcal{L}}_m \quad (36)$$

The corresponding first order perturbed equation is written under the hypothesis of an incompressible flow, related to the conservation of magnetic flux ensured by interchange instability :

$$\frac{\partial \delta M}{\partial t} + \frac{R\Omega}{h_\beta} \frac{\partial \delta M}{\partial \beta} + \frac{\delta v_\alpha}{h_\alpha} \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial \alpha} = 0 \quad (37)$$

Following Ferrière, Zimmer, et al. 2001, we assume periodic temporal variations for the perturbations, with frequency ω . This allows us to write equation 37 as a ordinate differential equation for δW with respect to β , which resolution yields the expression of the energy perturbation :

$$\delta M = \delta M_{\beta=0} \exp\left(\frac{i\omega\beta}{R_P\Omega}\right) - \frac{1}{R_P\Omega h_\alpha} \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial \alpha} \int_0^\beta \delta v_\alpha \exp\left(-\frac{i\omega}{R_P\Omega}(\beta' - \beta)\right) d\beta' \quad (38)$$

This expression is then injected in equation 43, resulting in :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \overline{\mathcal{F}}_{m,pu} - \overline{\mathcal{L}}_m &= \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial t} - B_{0,eq} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{h_\beta^2}{R_P \Omega} \langle \delta v_\alpha \int_0^\beta \delta v_\alpha \exp \left(-\frac{i\omega}{R\Omega} (\beta' - \beta) \right) d\beta' \rangle B_{0,eq} \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial \alpha} \right) \\
 &\quad - \frac{B_0}{R_P \Omega} \langle \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \left(\delta v_\beta \int_0^\beta \delta v_\alpha \exp \left(-\frac{i\omega}{R\Omega} (\beta' - \beta) \right) \right) \rangle \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial \alpha} \\
 &\quad + B_{0,eq} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(h_\beta \delta M_{\beta=0} \langle \delta v_\alpha e^{\frac{i\omega\beta}{R_P \Omega}} \rangle \right) + B_{0,eq} \langle \frac{\partial \delta v_\beta e^{\frac{i\omega\beta}{R_P \Omega}}}{\partial \beta} \rangle h_\alpha \delta M_{\beta=0}
 \end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

The first two terms of the right hand side of equation 39 correspond to a diffusive transport. As averages are performed azimuthally over 2π , the third and fifth terms are null. Neglecting the remaining third terms allows us to write a diffusion equation for the mass content of flux tubes :

$$\frac{\partial M_0}{\partial t} - B_{0,eq} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(D_\alpha B_{0,eq} \frac{\partial M_0}{\partial \alpha} \right) = \overline{\mathcal{F}}_{m,pu} - \overline{\mathcal{L}}_m \tag{40}$$

where the full expression of the diffusion coefficient is

$$D_\alpha = \frac{h_\beta^2}{R_P \Omega} \langle \delta v_\alpha \int_0^\beta \delta v_\alpha \exp \left(-\frac{i\omega}{R\Omega} (\beta' - \beta) \right) d\beta' \rangle \tag{41}$$

5.2 Transport of energy

Similarly to the previous analysis of the diffusion of the mass content, we derive here a transport equation for the energy content of flux tubes in the magnetosphere. The integrated entropy, also the amount of energy per particle in the flux tube, corrected from the adiabatic expansion of the flux tube, is

$$W = N k_B T V_0^{\gamma-1} \tag{42}$$

writing T the plasma temperature, γ the adiabatic exponent, and $V_0 = \int \frac{ds}{B}$ the flux tube volume. In the case of a thin disk, which applies well to the jovian magnetosphere and will be developed in section 6.2.2, an equivalent flux tube volume can be written in term of the disk scale height H , defined and computed in section 3 and figure 5 from the plasma equilibrium along field lines : $V_0 = \frac{H}{B_{0,eq}}$.

Under the assumption of an incompressible flow, the 2-D conservation equation for the energy content of flux tubes writes, integrating the source and loss term introduced in equation 5 over the flux tube :

$$\frac{DW}{Dt} = \frac{\partial W}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (W \mathbf{v}) = \overline{\mathcal{F}}_{q,pu} - \overline{\mathcal{L}}_q \tag{43}$$

We follow exactly the same steps as in the previous section. As equation 43 has exactly the same form as equation 35, this results in a diffusion equation for the energy content of flux tubes, using the same diffusion coefficient as for the mass :

$$\frac{\partial W_0}{\partial t} - B_{0,eq} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(D_\alpha B_{0,eq} \frac{\partial W_0}{\partial \alpha} \right) = \overline{\mathcal{F}}_{q,pu} - \overline{\mathcal{L}}_q \tag{44}$$

5.3 Transport of angular momentum

The equation of transport of momentum in the magnetosphere (equation 3) can be translated into an averaged infinitesimal transport equation for the angular momentum relative to the rotation axis of the

planet, noting that the torque of any force \mathbf{f} relative to this axis writes $= (\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{f}) \cdot \mathbf{e}_z = f_\beta R$. We write it, neglecting third-order terms and using equation (B.3) from Ferrière and Blanc 1996 to compute the spatial derivatives of the basis vectors :

$$\langle \delta \rho \delta \mathbf{v} \rangle \cdot \nabla (R v_\beta) = T_{L,z} + T_{pu,z} \quad (45)$$

where $T_{L,z} = -R \langle j_\alpha \rangle B_0$ and $T_{pu,z} = -R \langle j_{pu,\alpha} \rangle B_0$ are respectively the torque per unit volume due to the Lorentz force and the force associated to pick-up ; and the torques associated to the pressure gradient force and the gravitational force do not have a vertical component. We note that $R v_{\beta 0} = \Omega R^2$ is indeed the angular momentum per unit mass, and that the advection term driving the transport is a second order term linked to mass flow perturbations. Integrating the above over a flux shell yields the transport of angular momentum in the magnetosphere.

Let us consider the system shown in Figure 7. The sum of the Lorentz torque on the given flux shell, per unit flux, writes :

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathcal{T}_{L,z} &= \int_s \int_\beta T_{L,z} h_\alpha h_\beta d\beta ds d\alpha \\ &= -R_P d\alpha \int_s \int_0^{2\pi} j_\alpha R d\phi ds \\ &= R_P d\alpha \int \int \mathbf{j} \cdot d\mathbf{S} \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

It is thus directly linked to the flux of electromagnetic current through the flux shell. Hence, the transport of angular momentum in the magnetosphere can be analysed through the prism of the conservation of currents and the related theory of magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling. In the following, this latest approach will be used to derive a transport equation for the angular momentum.

In a steady-state, $\nabla \mathbf{j} = 0$ is integrated over the flux shell, yielding a relation between the magnetospheric transport of angular momentum through the magnetodisk currents, and the ionospheric integrated currents $J_{i\alpha,k}$ defined in section 2.3.2, in ionosphere $k = n$ or s :

$$\int \int_{S_{eq}} j_\alpha dS = -2\pi R_P (J_{i\alpha,n} + J_{i\alpha,s}) \quad (47)$$

The left hand side of equation 47 is linked to the transport equation 45 :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_{eq} &= - \int \int_0^{2\pi} j_\alpha R d\phi ds \\ &\simeq 2\pi \int \langle \delta \rho \delta \mathbf{v} \rangle \cdot \nabla (\Omega R^2) \frac{ds}{B_0} - 2\pi \int \langle j_{pu,\alpha} \rangle R ds \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

where the integral is done along field lines through the disk thickness. The above is then further developed in terms of local coordinates in order to obtain a form of the transport equation of angular momentum directly usable for theoretical and numerical applications. The advection term separates into two gradient terms for Ω and R . As Ω is constant along field lines, the previous integral becomes :

$$\mathcal{J}_{eq} = \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial \alpha} \int 2\pi \frac{R^2}{h_\alpha} \langle \delta \rho \delta v_\alpha \rangle \frac{ds}{B_0} + 2\Omega \int 2\pi R \langle \delta \rho \delta v_R \rangle \frac{ds}{B_0} - 2\pi \int \langle j_{pu,\alpha} \rangle R ds \quad (49)$$

All three terms of this sum correspond to specific aspects of the transport of angular momentum through the disk, which are further developed in the following.

Figure 7: Magnetic flux shell (dotted line) and the various currents flowing through the shell surface. The northern and southern ionospheric contributions are distinguished, the difference between them translates in different Pedersen conductances Σ_{Pn} and Σ_{Ps} in our model.

Perpendicular outflow The first integral term $\mathcal{I}_{eq,1} = \int 2\pi \frac{R^2}{h_\alpha} \langle \delta\rho \delta v_\alpha \rangle \frac{ds}{B}$ results from the term $\nabla\Omega$ in equation 48, and therefore corresponds to the variation of angular momentum of the plasma linked to the transport of flux tubes to a flux shell with a different rotation rate. In order to emphasise the perpendicular nature of this transport term, we write

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_\perp = \mathcal{I}_{eq,1} = \int 2\pi \frac{R^2}{h_\alpha} \langle \delta\rho \delta v_\alpha \rangle \frac{ds}{B_0} \quad (50)$$

$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_\perp$ has the dimension of a mass rate integrated over the disk height.

Radial outflow The second integral term $\mathcal{I}_{eq,2} = \int 2\pi R \langle \delta\rho \delta v_R \rangle \frac{ds}{B_0}$ is directly linked to the transport of the internal angular momentum of the flux tubes through the disk and has the dimension of a mass time rate of change per unit magnetic flux, integrated over the disk height. We write it $\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha} = \mathcal{I}_{eq,2}$ for clarity. Using the relation between the radial velocity v_R and the perpendicular velocity v_α at the position s on the field line given in equation A.3 (appendix A) leads to :

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha} = \int 2\pi \frac{R^2}{h_\alpha} \langle \delta\rho \left(h_\zeta \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial R} - h_\alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial R} \frac{B}{\rho} \int_{s_{eq}}^s \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} - \frac{\rho}{B} \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha} \right) \delta v_\alpha \right) \frac{ds'}{B} \right) \frac{ds'}{B} \quad (51)$$

where s_{eq} is the value of s at the equator.

Pick-up The last term $\mathcal{I}_{pu} = -2\pi \int \langle j_{pu,\alpha} \rangle R ds$ is related to the contribution of pick-up ions to the conservation of momentum. This contribution is due to the acceleration of new ions created by the ionisation of neutral in the magnetosphere from the near keplerian motion followed by neutrals with a velocity \mathbf{v}_n , to the motion of the plasma at the velocity \mathbf{v} . It is only present in the region of neutral sources in the disk, which are mainly the neutral tori in the vicinity of the active moons Enceladus and Io.

In the frame rotating with the neutral gas of the torus at a keplerian rotation rate $\Omega_K \simeq \sqrt{\frac{GM_P \sin(\theta)}{R^3}}$, the pick-up current is parallel to the electric field in the keplerian frame and can be expressed through the use of a *pick-up conductivity* $\mathbf{j}_{pu} = \sigma_{pu} \mathbf{E}'$ (see equation 1). Similarly to the derivation of the ionospheric perpendicular currents in section 2.3.2, we write $\mathbf{E}' = (\Omega_K - \Omega) R B \mathbf{e}_\alpha$. Assuming in addition that the neutral torus is thin, $\Omega_K \simeq \sqrt{\frac{GM}{R_{eq}^3}}$, $B_0 \simeq B_{0,eq}$ and the integral writes as a function of the pick-up conductance $\Sigma_{pu} = \int \sigma_{pu} ds$.

$$\mathcal{I}_{pu} = -2\pi(\Omega_K - \Omega) B_{0,eq} \Sigma_{pu} R_{eq}^2 \quad (52)$$

Depending on the prior knowledge one has of the system, it might be more convenient to express \mathcal{I}_{pu} as a function of the mass source $\mathcal{S}_{m,pu}$ due to pick-up, based on equation 1. \mathcal{I}_{pu} can then be written as the sum of an integrated source of angular momentum due to pick-up, and a correction for the keplerian momentum, which the neutral had before being ionised :

$$\mathcal{I}_{pu} = \dot{\mathcal{M}}_{pu/\alpha} \Omega - \mathcal{L}_{kepler} \quad (53)$$

where $\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{pu/\alpha} = \int 2\pi R^2 \mathcal{S}_{m,pu} \frac{ds}{B_0}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{kepler} = \int 2\pi R \mathcal{S}_{m,pu} \sqrt{\frac{GM_P}{r}} \frac{ds}{B}$.

Using equations 50, 51 and 52, and the relation between the rotation rate of the magnetospheric plasma and the electrostatic potential at the equator ($\frac{\partial \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha} = R_P \Omega$), equation 47 finally writes :

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_\perp \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha^2} + 2\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha} \frac{\partial \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha} - 2\pi \left(\Omega_K R_P - \frac{\partial \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha} \right) B_{0,eq} \Sigma_{pu} R_{eq}^2 = -2\pi R_P (J_{i\alpha,n} + J_{i\alpha,s}) \quad (54)$$

5.4 Summary

The perturbation of the equilibrium state of the magnetosphere has been investigated in this section. In our framework, this perturbation is linked to a specific instability, naming the flux tube interchange instability, which develop in magnetised media embedded in a centrifugal potential, and is characterised by an outwards diffusion of plasma conserving the magnetic flux. The resulting transport conserves the integrated mass, energy and angular momentum of flux tubes. We first integrated the local mass conservation and adiabatic equations (2 and 5) along field lines to write conservation equations for the total mass and energy contents of flux tubes. From there, the quasi-linear approach allowed us to derive two diffusion equations for the integral mass and energy (equations 40 and 44), introducing a diffusion coefficient D_α of which spatial dependence would require ad-hoc specification.

The transport of the angular momentum content of the flux tubes differ from that of the mass and the energy. Additionally to flux tube exchange, it is indeed driven by angular momentum exchange between the ionosphere and the magnetosphere, as shown in section 5.3. We derive a relation between the electrostatic potential at the equator, linked to the plasma rotation rate and angular momentum through $\frac{\partial \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha} = R_P \Omega$, and the electric current flux through the flux shell in the ionosphere. Both are coupled by the mean of field-aligned currents loops connecting the ionosphere and the magnetodisk. A full derivation of the system of equations describing the transport of angular momentum through the magnetosphere requires further analysis of the magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling and is done in the next section.

6 M-I coupling

This section aims at deriving an equation for the radial transport of angular momentum through the magnetosphere from the local conservation of momentum in the magnetosphere (equation 3). Such an equation has been obtained by Hill 1979 and Pontius 1997, based on the macroscopic torque balance written on a magnetic flux shell in the limit of an infinitely thin disk in the absence of plasma sources or sinks. The Hill-Pontius equation, which is a reference equation for studying the radial variation of

the rotation rate and the magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling around gas giants, has been developed into more elaborate models by Cowley and Bunce 2001, Achilleos, Guio, et al. 2010, Nichols 2011. However, the above-mentioned works all approximated magnetic field lines as perfect conductors and neglected the effect of field-aligned potential drops as potential source of electronic acceleration at high latitude and decoupling between the ionosphere and the magnetosphere (Wang et al. 2021). More recently, Ray, Ergun, et al. 2010 self-consistently computed field-aligned current loop and magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling including the effect on field-aligned potential drops, not only on the mapping between the magnetodisk and magnetically conjugated ionosphere, but also on the field-aligned current intensity and the ionospheric resistive properties (Pedersen conductance).

We first derive a system of equations describing the exchange of angular momentum between the magnetodisk and the ionosphere, self-consistently taking into account the influence of field-aligned potential drops, in section 6.1. We then show a certain number of useful approximations, in particular to cases corresponding to the magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn in section 6. Based on those approximations, section 6.3 shows a full numerical application of simplified equations for the jovian magnetosphere.

6.1 The M-I coupling system

The radial variation of the total angular momentum of a flux shell has been linked to the closing of field-aligned current loops between the magnetodisk and the planet ionosphere in section 5.3. In the following, we self-consistently take into account the effect of field-aligned potential drops in the exchange of angular momentum between the ionosphere and the magnetosphere to complete the derivation of angular momentum transport in the magnetosphere. It results in a system of five equations coupling five variables :

- the equatorial electric potential in the planetocentric inertial frame Φ_{eq} , related to the angular rotation rate through Ω
- the ionospheric electric potentials in the planetocentric inertial frame in both hemispheres Φ_{in} and Φ_{is}
- the ionospheric field aligned currents in both hemispheres $j_{\parallel,in}$ and $j_{\parallel,is}$

First, combining equation 54 with the expression of the integrated ionospheric perpendicular currents given by equation 10 results in a relation between all three electrostatic potentials at the equator (linked to the plasma rotation rate through $R_P\Omega = \frac{\partial\Phi_{eq}}{\partial\alpha}$), and in the ionospheres :

$$\mathcal{M}_{\perp} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha^2} + 2\mathcal{M}_{R/\alpha} \frac{\partial \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha} - 2\pi \left(\Omega_K R_P - \frac{\partial \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha} \right) B_{0,eq} \Sigma_{pu} R_{eq}^2 = 2\pi \sum_{k=n,s} \left(\Omega_P R_P - \frac{\partial \Phi_k}{\partial \alpha} \right) \frac{\Sigma_{Pk} R_{ik}^2 B_{ik}}{\sin(I_k)} \quad (55)$$

To complete this system, we introduce two additional unknowns, the field-aligned currents in both ionospheres. The null divergence of currents, $B \frac{\partial j_{\parallel}/B}{\partial s} = -\nabla_{\perp} \cdot \mathbf{j}_{\perp}$, allows us to compute integrated field-aligned currents in each ionosphere $k = n$ or s as a function of the integrated perpendicular currents introduced in section 2.3.2 :

$$j_{\parallel,ik} = \int_s j_{\zeta} ds = -B_{ik} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\int_s h_{\beta} j_{\alpha} ds \right) = -B_{ik} \frac{\partial J_{\alpha,ik}}{\partial \alpha} \quad (56)$$

Equations 10 and 56 allow us to write a first relation between ionospheric field-aligned currents and the corresponding ionospheric electrostatic potentials in each ionosphere :

$$j_{\parallel,ik} = -B_{ik} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\left(\Omega_P R_P - \frac{\partial \Phi_{ik}}{\partial \alpha} \right) \frac{\Sigma_{Pk} B_{ik} \sin(\theta_{ik})^2}{\sin(I_k)} \right), \quad k = n \text{ or } s \quad (57)$$

The system is finally closed through two current-voltage equations linking the field-aligned currents and the field-aligned potential drops $\Phi_{\parallel k} = \Phi_{ik} - \Phi_{eq}$ in both ionospheres $k = n$ or s , $j_{\parallel k} = K(\Phi_{\parallel k})$, shown in more details in section 2.3.3.

6.2 Useful approximations

6.2.1 Perfectly conducting field lines

Neglecting the field-aligned potential drops allows us to write a direct relation between the ionospheric electric fields and the rotation rate Ω (equation 11). Equation 55 then becomes a coupling relation between the magnetospheric rotation rate and ionospheric quantities:

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{\perp} \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial \alpha} + 2\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha} \Omega = 2\pi \sum_{k=n,s} R_{ik}^2 B_{ik} \frac{\Sigma_{Pk}}{\sin(I_k)} (\Omega_P - \Omega) + 2\pi B_{0,eq} R_{eq}^2 \Sigma_{pu} (\Omega_K - \Omega) \quad (58)$$

This equation is in general agreement with the result from Hill 1979 and Pontius 1997. However, we have extended their result to the case of a thick disk and potentially extended source regions, making use of two integrated mass outflow rates $\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{\perp}$ and $\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha}$, and terms linked to the addition of momentum to the system by pick-up processes. Equation 58 suggests a natural interpretation of angular momentum transport in the disk as the result of the coupling between a region of radial angular momentum outflow and three resistive regions characterised by their conductances : the northern and southern ionospheres, and the pick-up source region.

A straight-forward application of equation 58 is the computation of the rotation rate of the field lines in the absence of plasma outflow ($\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{\perp} = \dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha} = 0$) :

$$\Omega^* = \frac{B_{0,eq} R_{eq}^2 \Sigma_{pu} \Omega_K + \sum_{k=n,s} R_{ik}^2 B_{ik} \frac{\Sigma_{Pk}}{\sin(I_k)} \Omega_P}{B_{0,eq} R_{eq}^2 \Sigma_{pu} + \sum_{k=n,s} R_{ik}^2 B_{ik} \frac{\Sigma_{Pk}}{\sin(I_k)}} \quad (59)$$

In the absence of pick-up, the rotation rate is equal to that of the upper atmosphere. The addition of a pick-up source results in a competition between the ionospheric resistances rotating at Ω_P and the pick-up resistance rotating at Ω_K , and the rotation rate of the field lines is a weighted mean of the two rotation rates, which naturally varies with R_{eq} .

6.2.2 Limit case of a thin disk

Considering the limit of a thin disk allows us to recover the result of Ray, Ergun, et al. 2010. It will be useful for further comparison of our model to the existing literature and data on Jupiter's magnetosphere. In such a case, in the equatorial integral \mathcal{I}_{eq} , all variables can be approximated by their equatorial values. In particular, $v_R \sim -v_{\alpha}$ and $\dot{M} = -\langle 2\pi R_{eq} H \rho v_{\alpha} \rangle$, H being the thickness of the disk. The mass outflow terms becomes :

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{\perp} \simeq -\dot{M} \frac{R_{eq}^2}{R_P}$$

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha} \simeq -\frac{\langle 2\pi R_{eq} H \rho v_{\alpha} \rangle}{B_{0,eq}} \simeq \frac{\dot{M}}{B_{0,eq}}$$

Using the above in equation 55 leads to :

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha^2} - \frac{2R_P}{R_{eq}^2 B_{0,eq}} \frac{\partial \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha} + 2\pi R_P \left(\Omega_K R_P - \frac{\partial \Phi_{eq}}{\partial \alpha} \right) \frac{B_{0,eq} \Sigma_{pu}}{M} = -2\pi R_P \sum_{k=n,s} \left(\Omega_{nk} R_P - \frac{\partial \Phi_k}{\partial \alpha} \right) \frac{\Sigma_{Pk} R_{ik}^2 B_{ik}}{R_{eq}^2 M \sin(I_k)} \quad (60)$$

This relation, together with equations 57 and 14 leads to a system which is very similar to that solved by Ray, Ergun, et al. 2010. However, their result is extended to the case of inter-hemispheric asymmetries.

6.2.3 Limit case of a dipolar field

At Saturn, the magnetic field can be well approximated at all radii by a dipolar magnetic field. This allows us to express the integrated transport quantities $\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{\perp}$ and $\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha}$ in terms of the total perpendicular mass outflow \dot{M} , using prior knowledge on the equilibrium state quantities ρ and B . The underlying assumption is that the plasma β is low so the field lines are not strongly bent by the plasma dynamics. Henceforth, $\frac{D\alpha}{Dt} = \frac{v_{\alpha}}{h_{\alpha}}$ is conserved along a field line. The total perpendicular mass outflow then writes :

$$\dot{M} = \int 2\pi R \langle \rho v_{\alpha} \rangle ds = -2\pi R_P \langle \frac{v_{\alpha}}{h_{\alpha}} M_{FT} \rangle$$

where $M_{FT} = \int \rho \frac{ds}{B_0}$ is the mass integrated over a flux tube, per unit flux. Then,

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{\perp} = 2\pi \langle \frac{v_{\alpha}}{h_{\alpha}} I_{FT} \rangle = -\frac{I_{FT} \dot{M}}{R_P M_{FT}} \quad (61)$$

where $I_{FT} = \int R^2 \rho \frac{ds}{B_0}$ is the moment of inertia of a flux tube, and the above derivation assumes that $\langle v_{\alpha} \rho \rangle = v_{\alpha} \rho$. Additionally, using the dipolar field relations allows us to give an expression of $\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha}$ directly applicable for numerical integration of the system. It writes, using the spherical coordinates (r, θ) :

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{R/\alpha} = - \left(\int \frac{\rho}{B_0^2} (1 - 3 \cos^2(\theta)) r \frac{d\theta}{\sin(\theta)} + \int \frac{3r^2 \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta)}{R_P} \int \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{\rho}{B_0} \right) ds' d\theta \right) \frac{\dot{M}}{M_{FT}} \quad (62)$$

where,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{\rho}{B_0} \right) = \frac{1}{B_0} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} - \frac{\rho}{B_0^2} \frac{3R_P}{r^2} \left(\frac{\sqrt{3 \cos^2(\theta) + 1}}{\sin(\theta)^2} - \frac{\cos(\theta) \sin(\theta)^2}{2\sqrt{3 \cos^2(\theta) + 1}} \right)$$

Injecting relations 61 and 62 in equation 55 hence yields an expression of the M-I coupling system from physical integrated quantities as the integrated mass and angular momentum on a flux tube. Computing those integral quantities required prior knowledge on the equilibrium 2D configuration of the magnetosphere, in particular the distribution of the plasma density along field lines, and the topology of the magnetic field. Those distributions can be computed from equations 18, 17 and 32 and the knowledge of the equatorial variation profiles of thermodynamical quantities. Self-consistently solving the M-I coupling system requires additional equations providing the equatorial radial profiles of such quantities.

6.3 Jupiter's magnetosphere

The jovian magnetosphere is characterised by a thin plasma disk, confined at the equator by the fast rotation of field lines. The system described in section 6.2.2, can be applied to compute the rotation curve in the jovian magnetosphere self-consistently taking into account the finite conductivity of field lines, given a certain magnetic field topology and a constant mass outflow through the magnetosphere (justified by the confined plasma source located on Io's orbit in the inner regions).

However, we first provide a very simplified model of the magnetosphere, neglecting field-aligned potential drops and using equation 58, which allows to write a single equation for the angular momentum transport :

$$\dot{M} \left(\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial \alpha} - \frac{2R_P}{R_{eq}^2 B_{0,eq}} \Omega \right) = -2\pi R_P (\Omega_K - \Omega) B_{0,eq} \Sigma_{pu} - 2\pi R_P \sum_{k=n,s} (\Omega_{Pk} - \Omega) \frac{\Sigma_{Pk} R_{ik}^2 B_{ik}}{R_{eq}^2 \sin(I_k)} \quad (63)$$

We recover an equation which is analogous to the equation derived by Hill 1979 and Pontius 1997 assuming a thin plasma sheet at the equator. The authors made the additional assumptions that the magnetic field in the ionosphere is equal to its radial component ($\sin(I_n) \sim \sin(I_s) \sim 1$) and that the northern and southern hemispheres are symmetrical, yielding $\frac{\Sigma_{Pn}}{\sin(I_n)^2} + \frac{\Sigma_{Ps}}{\sin(I_s)^2} = 2\Sigma_P$, where Σ_P is the conductance of the ionosphere, equal for both hemispheres. The symmetry between the northern and southern ionospheres additionally yields $\mathbf{B}_{0,eq} \parallel \mathbf{e}_\theta$ and allows them to write $\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} = -\frac{R_P}{R_{eq} B_{0,eq}} \frac{\partial}{\partial R_{eq}}$ in the left hand side of equation 63.

Equation 63 is integrated using a simple ordinal differential equation solver to compute rotation profiles assuming a constant mass outflow \dot{M} with R_{eq} and no source term. The solution is thus valid outside the Io torus, and is derived from $6R_J$. At $6R_J$, the plasma is assumed to be fully co-rotating with the planet.

The code is first validated against the results of Cowley, Bunce, and Nichols 2003 in figure 8, comparing the CAN-KK magnetic field model and the dipolar model. For the CAN-KK model, we used the formula provided by Ray, Ergun, et al. 2010 on the basis of the work of Cowley and Bunce 2001 and follow up. The model is then used to investigate the effects of inter-hemispheric asymmetries on the rotation curve in figure 9. As a direct follow up to the comments given in section 6.2.1 on the formalisation of magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling as the competing rotations of three resistances at different rates, we show the effects of variable ionospheric conductances but also ionospheric rotation rates Ω_{ns} and Ω_{nn} (replacing Ω_P in equation 63).

Figure 8: *Left* : Rotation curves for the present model of the Jovian magnetosphere, assuming a dipolar (dotted line) and the CAN-KK (full line) magnetic field model, compared to the analytical solution for the dipole model provided by Cowley, Bunce, and Nichols 2003 (dashed line). *Right* : Rotation curve obtained by Cowley, Bunce, and Nichols 2003, assuming a dipolar (analytical solution, dashed line) or their own empirical model (full line).

(a) Σ_{Pn} is varied, keeping $\Sigma_{Ps} = 0.5 \text{ mho}$ and $\Omega_{nn} = \Omega_{ns} = \Omega_J$. (b) Ω_{nn} is varied, keeping $\Omega_{ns} = \Omega_J$ and $\Sigma_{Pn} = \Sigma_{Ps} = 0.5 \text{ mho}$. (c) Σ_{Pn} is varied, keeping $\Sigma_{Ps} = 0.5 \text{ mho}$ and $\Omega_{ns} = \Omega_J = 2\Omega_{nn}$.

Figure 9: Rotation curves computed by integrating equation 63 from $6R_J$ to $60R_J$. The inner boundary condition is $\Omega = \Omega_J$ at $6R_J$. The magnetic field model is taken from Ray, Ergun, et al. 2010, and combines the CAN model (Connerney et al. 1981) bellow $21.78R_P$, and the Khurana and Kivelson 1993 model above $21.78R_P$.

6.4 Summary

We self consistently included the effects of field-aligned potential drop in the transport of angular momentum in the magnetosphere by deriving a closed set of equations coupling five variables : the field-aligned currents in each ionosphere $j_{\parallel, in}$ and $j_{\parallel, is}$, the ionospheric and equatorial electric potentials in the planetocentric inertial frame Φ_{in} , Φ_{is} and Φ_{eq} . Those five variables are coupled through one equation for the current continuity in the magnetosphere (equation 55), two equations for the current continuity in both ionospheres (equation 57) and two current-voltage relations for both hemispheres (equation 14). The resolution of this system yields a solution for the evolution of the angular momentum of flux tubes through the disk through the relation between the equatorial electrostatic potential Φ_{eq} and the magnetospheric rotation rate Ω .

The formalisation of magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling can be simplified in a certain number of limit cases. First, neglecting field-aligned potential drops and assuming perfectly conducting field lines allows us to replace the M-I coupling system by a single equation linking the magnetospheric variation of the plasma rotation rate to the ionospheric properties, in the form of equation 58. This equation is a generalisation of the result of Hill 1979 and Pontius 1997 to the case of a disk of finite thickness. On the other hand, in the limit cases of a thin disk, corresponding to the jovian magnetodisk, or a dipolar magnetic field, corresponding to the kronian magnetospheric environment, the integrated outflows can be directly linked to the total mass outflow profile in the magnetosphere, which allows numerical resolution of the M-I coupling system. For instance, assuming an infinitely thin equatorial disk as well as perfectly conducting magnetic field lines allows us to provide a first numerical solution for the rotation curve in the jovian magnetosphere.

Further applications, for instance to the case of Saturn, will require the combination of the M-I coupling system to the diffusion equations for the mass and the energy derived in section 5. The kronian magnetosphere indeed shows extended plasma sources, and thus a variable total mass outflow \dot{M} with distance to the planet. In addition, the self-consistent inclusion of the magnetic field and the plasma distribution requires to combine transport equations to the description of the equilibrium magnetospheric configuration developed in sections 3 and 4.

7 Conclusion

Theoretical modelling the magnetospheres of the gas giants in the Solar System can be traced back as far as 1975 and the first tentative models of the magnetic field of Jupiter based on Pioneer data by e.g. Barish and Smith 1975. Nevertheless, no self-consistent theoretical description of the magnetospheres of Jupiter and Saturn, including the thickness of their magnetodisk, its coupling to the planetary rotation, the nature of transport processes and the presence of plasma source and sinks, has yet been achieved. Models of transport in these magnetospheres and their magnetodisks either account for the coupling between the planet and the equatorial plasma and its influence on transport, neglecting the thickness and plasma temperature of the disk and using ad-hoc transport quantities ; or they focus on a description of the physical quantities in the disk, including its thickness and temperature, but overlook its interaction with the planet's upper atmosphere.

This internship proposes a first tentative self-consistent model of radial transport of the angular momentum, mass and energy contents of flux tubes in the gas giant magnetospheres in the form of a set of ten equations. Limiting the study to the inner and middle magnetosphere, we treat a simplified axisymmetric magnetosphere, and take into account the latitudinal extent of the magnetodisk and potentially extended source and sink regions.

The equilibrium state of the magnetosphere is first described by three equations (17, 18 and 32) providing the topology of the magnetic field and the distribution of plasma along field lines in sections 3 and 4. The analysis of the field-aligned component allowed us to derive analytical expressions for the thickness of the disk.

In order to self-consistently characterise the radial evolution of plasma properties in the disk, we then introduced and studied quasi-static perturbations of the equilibrium state. Two diffusion equations are derived for the total mass and energy content of flux tubes in section 5, namely equations 40 and 44. Both equations would allow the derivation of radial density and temperature profiles, taking into account extended plasma and energy sources and losses in the magnetosphere.

As discussed in section 5.3, the transport of angular momentum requires a different approach based on the magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling. Our main result concerns the derivation of a coupled system of five equations (14, 55 and 57) accounting for the transport of angular momentum in section 6. We were able to generalise previous results from Hill 1979 and Pontius 1997, used in the more recent studies of e.g. Cowley and Bunce 2001, Nichols 2011 and Ray, Ergun, et al. 2010, to a disk of finite thickness presenting an arbitrary distribution of plasma sources, as well as field-aligned potential drop and inter-hemispheric asymmetries. We showed that the transport of angular momentum in the magnetosphere is linked to an interplay between three resistive regions : the northern and southern ionosphere, and the pick-up source region, through field-aligned currents coupling the magnetodisk to the ionosphere of the planet. Our results allows for instance a more consistent modelling of the effects of the neutral tori surrounding Io and Enceladus by taking into account their radial and latitudinal extent (illustrated in figure 1). A by-product of this derivation is the computation of field-aligned currents in the ionospheric region, which is of main interest in the understanding of auroral phenomena and of the observed North-South asymmetry of Jupiter's (Kotsiaros et al. 2019) and Saturn's (Nakamura et al. 2019) auroras.

Coupling the diffusion equations and the magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling system will allow numerical applications of our present model in the simpler case of a centrifugally confined magnetodisk or that of a dipolar field (discussed in section 6). As a result, quantities such as the total mass outflow and heating rate in the system can be derived from rotation and temperature profiles, or, conversely, rotation curves and temperature profiles can be computed from prior estimates of sources and diffusion coefficients. A first simple example of numerical solution for the case of a thin disk, with no source term and perfectly conducting field lines, corresponding to Jupiter, is shown and paves the way for future, more complex, numerical modelling.

A lot is yet to be done to conclude this work and validate our model. First, numerical integration of the above set of equations in the various limit cases must be performed on the basis of our first numerical example, in order to compare the results to previous studies (Achilleos, Guio, et al. 2010, Ray, Ergun, et al. 2010 ...) and data. Second, further work is needed to connect all our equations together and achieve a self consistent model of radial transport in the magnetosphere of gas giants. In particular, the coupling between the transport equations and the equilibrium state equations is yet to be investigated and applied numerically.

Our system for the magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling (section 6) paves the way for many interesting applications. It can be used for instance to study the North-South asymmetry in the Jovian and Kronian magnetospheres and auroras. Acting on the pick-up source properties would also allow to investigate to some extent the temporal variability of the gas giants magnetosphere in the limit of quasi-static temporal evolution.

Our knowledge on gas giant systems is expected to greatly improve in the coming years thanks to the extended Juno mission as well as the future JUICE and Europa-Clipper missions to Jupiter, under preparation by ESA and NASA, respectively. The Juno mission has already provided precious insight in the jovian system on a large variety of aspects : magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling, transport of plasma, interaction with satellites... It allows ever more accurate measurements of the plasma distribution in the magnetosphere, the structure of the current sheet as well as rotation and temperature profiles, as exemplified in figure 10. Comparing the various outputs of our model to the numerous observables derived from Juno observations will allow us to further constrain the physics of transport processes in the Jovian magnetosphere using the more elaborate formulation of plasma diffusion we started to develop.

In addition, the JUICE and Europa-Clipper missions are expected to provide precious data on the evolution of the Jovian magnetosphere and its interaction with the various moons, which could then feed our model and lead to an always-more-precise understanding of the physical processes at stake.

Our model of radial outflow in a magnetised thick plasma sheet finds multiple echos in the studies of magnetised disks at various scales (e.g. Batygin and Morbidelli 2020). It contributes to the more general understanding of astrophysical disks by investigating the physical processes at play in the specific framework of giant planet systems, using the powerful in-situ investigation techniques provided by planetary missions.

(a) Figure 9 of Huscher et al. 2021.

(b) Figure 5.A of Huscher et al. 2021.

(c) Figure 2 of Liu et al. 2021.

(d) Figure 7 of Kim et al. 2020.

Figure 10: Recent Juno measurements providing the meridian distribution of ions (a) illustrate the vertical extent of the current sheet and indicate, along with the derivation of its thickness from magnetic field inversion (b and c), the confined nature of the disk in the Jovian magnetosphere. Measurements of the rotation curve and of the temperature profile by the same probe, given in panel d, show how the rotation curve progressively departs from rigid corotation with increasing radial distance and provide valuable input for transport modelling in the Jovian magnetosphere.

Appendices

A Linking radial and perpendicular velocity

In the following, the expression of the radial velocity v_R as a function of the perpendicular velocity v_α is derived. In order to do so, we study the motion of a parcel of plasma through flux shells. The total mass of a flux tube segment from the equator (at s_{eq}) to the abscissa s is defined as

$$m(\alpha, s) = \int_{s_{eq}}^s \rho \frac{ds'}{B} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

During the motion of a flux tube segment from α to $\alpha + d\alpha$ in the magnetosphere, this quantity is conserved and the segment expands parallel to the field lines as illustrated in figure 11, such that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= m(\alpha + d\alpha, s + ds) - m(\alpha, s) \\ &= d\alpha \frac{\partial m}{\partial \alpha}(\alpha, s) + ds \frac{\partial m}{\partial s}(\alpha, s) + O(d\alpha^2, ds^2, d\alpha ds) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 11: Motion of a parcel of plasma through flux shells in the magnetosphere. The parcel, located at the position (α, s) moves by $d\mathbf{r}$ through a quasi-static transformation, such that it is always in the hydrostatic equilibrium. This means that the mass $m(\alpha, s)$ which supports the parcel at t is the same as the mass $m(\alpha + d\alpha, s + ds)$ which supports it at $t + dt$.

It allows to write $v_{\parallel} = \frac{ds}{dt}$ in terms of $v_\alpha = h_\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{dt}$ as $v_{\parallel} = -\frac{\partial m}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{\partial m}{\partial s} \right)^{-1} v_\alpha$. As $\frac{\partial m}{\partial \alpha} = \int_{s_{eq}}^s \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{\rho}{B} \right) ds'$ and $\frac{\partial m}{\partial s} = \frac{\rho}{B}$, the latter writes :

$$v_{\parallel} = -\frac{B}{\rho} \int_{s_{eq}}^s \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} - \frac{\rho}{B} \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha} \right) \frac{ds'}{B} v_\alpha \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Finally, we express v_R in terms of v_{\parallel} and v_α . We note that $\mathbf{e}_\alpha = h_\alpha \nabla \alpha$, yielding $\mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}_R = h_\alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial R}$, and,

similarly, $\mathbf{e}_\zeta \cdot \mathbf{e}_R = h_\zeta \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial R}$. Then $v_R = v_\alpha h_\alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial R} + v_\parallel h_\zeta \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial R}$. Using equation A.2 finally leads to :

$$v_R = \left(h_\zeta \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial R} - h_\alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial R} \frac{B}{\rho} \int_{s_{eq}}^s \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} - \frac{\rho}{B} \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha} \right) \frac{ds'}{B} \right) v_\alpha \quad (\text{A.3})$$

B Field-aligned currents in the magnetosphere

B.1 General vectorial equation

Following the work from Caudal and Blanc 1988, we give a vectorial expression of the variation of field-aligned currents along field lines based on the conservation of momentum. The non-divergence of currents separates into field-aligned and perpendicular terms as follows :

$$B \frac{\partial j_\parallel / B}{\partial s} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{j}_\perp$$

Taking the product of \mathbf{B} with equation 3 yields :

$$\rho \mathbf{B} \times (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} = -\mathbf{B} \times \nabla P + B^2 \mathbf{j}_\perp$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} B \frac{\partial j_\parallel}{\partial s} &= -\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\rho}{B^2} \mathbf{B} \times (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{B}}{B^2} \times \nabla P \right) \\ &= -\frac{\rho}{B^2} \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{B} \times (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}) - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\rho}{B^2} \right) \cdot (\mathbf{B} \times (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}) - \frac{1}{B^2} \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{B} \times \nabla P) - (\mathbf{B} \times \nabla P) \cdot \nabla \frac{1}{B^2} \\ &= -\frac{1}{B^2} (\rho (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} + \nabla P) \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{B} + \frac{\rho}{B^2} \mathbf{B} \cdot (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) (\nabla \times \mathbf{v}) - \frac{1}{B^2} \nabla \rho \cdot (\mathbf{B} \times (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}) \\ &\quad + 2 \frac{\rho}{B^3} \nabla B \cdot (\mathbf{B} \times (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}) + \frac{2}{B^2} \nabla B \cdot (\mathbf{B} \times \nabla P) \end{aligned}$$

As $(\rho (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} + \nabla P) \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} (\mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot \mathbf{j} = 0$, the equation becomes :

$$B \frac{\partial j_\parallel / B}{\partial s} = \frac{2}{B^3} \mathbf{B} \cdot (\nabla P \times \mathbf{B}) + \frac{\rho}{B^2} \mathbf{B} \cdot (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) (\nabla \times \mathbf{v}) + \frac{2\rho}{B^3} (\nabla B \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} - \frac{1}{B^2} (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \cdot (\nabla \rho \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (\text{B.1})$$

B.2 Curvilinear coordinates

We want to write equation B.1 using the curvilinear coordinates. We first compute each term individually. Assuming that $\frac{\partial B}{\partial \phi} = 0$, the first term is:

$$\mathbf{B} \cdot (\nabla P \times \mathbf{B}) = -\frac{B^2}{R_P} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \phi} \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha}$$

We then use the expression of the advection in the cylindrical coordinates

$$(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} = \left(v_R \frac{\partial v_R}{\partial R} + \Omega \frac{\partial v_R}{\partial \phi} - \Omega^2 R \right) \mathbf{e}_R + v_R \left(2\Omega + R \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial R} \right) \mathbf{e}_\phi$$

to compute the third and fourth terms :

$$\begin{aligned} (\nabla B \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} &= -\frac{B^2 R v_R}{R_P} \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha} \left(2\Omega + R \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial R} \right) (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \cdot (\nabla \rho \times \mathbf{B}) \\ &= -\frac{B^2 R v_R}{R_P} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} \left(2\Omega + R \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial R} \right) + \frac{B}{R} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \phi} \left(v_R \frac{\partial v_R}{\partial R} + \Omega \frac{\partial v_R}{\partial \phi} - \Omega^2 R \right) \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{e}_\alpha \end{aligned}$$

Finally, assuming that $v_z \sim 0$ and $\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial z} \sim 0$ for all velocity components $i=R, \phi$ in the plasma disk,

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{v} = \left(2\Omega + R \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial R} - \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial v_R}{\partial \phi} \right) \mathbf{e}_z$$

Thus, using the relation $\mathbf{e}_z \cdot \mathbf{e}_\zeta = \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{e}_\alpha$, the second term of equation B.1 writes

$$\mathbf{B} \cdot (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) (\nabla \times \mathbf{v}) = \left(3v_R \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial R} + Rv_R \frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial R^2} + \frac{v_R}{R^2} \frac{\partial v_R}{\partial \phi} - \frac{v_R}{R} \frac{\partial^2 v_R}{\partial R \partial \phi} - \frac{\Omega}{R} \frac{\partial^2 v_R}{\partial \phi^2} \right) \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{e}_\alpha$$

We then combine all terms to write the full equation in curvilinear coordinates :

$$\begin{aligned} B \frac{\partial j_{\parallel} / B}{\partial s} = & - \frac{2}{BR_P} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \phi} \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha} + \frac{Rv_R}{R_P} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} - \frac{2\rho}{B} \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha} \right) \left(2\Omega + R \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial R} \right) \\ & + \frac{\rho}{B} \left(3v_R \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial R} + Rv_R \frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial R^2} + \frac{v_R}{R^2} \frac{\partial v_R}{\partial \phi} - \frac{v_R}{R} \frac{\partial^2 v_R}{\partial R \partial \phi} - \frac{\Omega}{R} \frac{\partial^2 v_R}{\partial \phi^2} \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{v_R}{R\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \phi} \frac{\partial v_R}{\partial R} - \frac{\Omega}{R\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \phi} \frac{\partial v_R}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\Omega^2}{\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \phi} \right) \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{e}_\alpha \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The above equation simplifies greatly if all azimuthal variations are neglected, i.e. the system presents a perfect cylindrical symmetry :

$$B \frac{\partial j_{\parallel} / B}{\partial s} = \frac{Rv_R}{R_P} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} - \frac{2\rho}{B} \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha} \right) \left(2\Omega + R \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial R} \right) + \frac{\rho}{B} \left(3v_R \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial R} + Rv_R \frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial R^2} \right) \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{e}_\alpha \quad (\text{B.3})$$

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